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Abstract

This deliverable presents the planned testing approach for the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) of the Agora of acceleration services. It outlines the structure, methodology, and key evaluation criteria for assessing the services' usability, effectiveness, and impact on institutional transformation. The document details the testing process, specifying the activities to be carried out, the methodology to follow, the intended timeline, and the key performance indicators (KPIs) that will guide the evaluation. The planned tests aim to gather actionable insights to refine the MVS and ensure its alignment with user needs and institutional objectives. The testing outcomes will identify potential improvements, assess alignment with user needs and perceived value, and highlight usability issues, adoption barriers, and areas for refinement. This will ensure a more seamless user experience while evaluating the service's impact on institutional processes, decision-making, and stakeholder engagement. The results of these tests will not only inform the evolution of the services and platform but will also influence the work of other work packages, guiding further development and the strategic direction of the project.

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Document Updates

This revised version of the deliverable incorporates the feedback from the European Commission, addressing the following inquiry:

“The definition of the stakeholders and users involved in the process the extended stakeholders nature is unclear. On page 17 they are defined as part of the Alliances for which the Agora is developed but two pages later they are supposed to include also non-University ones like citizens, public administration and industry and businesses. This is however the only place where this complementary profiles are mentioned as, in the rest of the report it appears that only the Universities stakeholders will be engaged in the validation activities. This aspect should be clarified or better described.”

This document now explicitly addresses the comment on page 18, in the paragraph “2.3 Stakeholders and users involved in the process”, where we clarify that within the extended stakeholder group, we specifically target “Allies”—stakeholders such as alliances and consortia of universities that have already expressed interest in receiving a tailored version of the Agora platform and in co-creating its acceleration services with us. We also indicate the possibility of involving other extended stakeholders in certain activities, if and when specific services are developed that directly target them—something that, at this stage, is not yet the case. Furthermore, on page 20, we ensured consistency in the paragraph “Universities involved

in the testing activities.” As described in the paragraph on the “Timeline”, the testing cycles are structured around the target university alliances. We explain that we are testing with universities and alliances because they have co-created the services and the project follows a design thinking approach. However, during the third cycle, we may also include extended users who are currently not involved—provided that new services are developed during the project that specifically target them. In that case, it will be necessary to engage them in selected activities to gather complementary feedback.

Abbreviation list

aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
DMP	Data Management Plan
D2.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D5 from WP2, Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue
D4.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D10 from WP4, Inventory, Action plan and preliminary set of processes
D7.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D18 from WP7, First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
HEI	Higher Education Institution
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MVS	Minimum Viable Solution
OA	Open Access
VS	Viable Solution
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

This document presents the detailed plan for testing the **Minimum Viable Solution (MVS)** of the Agora of Acceleration Services. It outlines the testing objectives, methodology, plan and expected outcomes, building upon the preliminary framework described in **D6.1 – Draft Report about the Planned Test with User Groups**.

This document details the work of WP6, "*Testing acceleration services and assessment of the user groups' progress in the institutional transformations*", whose main goal is to test the joint output of WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5. The planned testing process is structured around seven key phases, developed using the Design Thinking methodology, as described in Section 5 of D2.1. These phases include: (1) engaging stakeholders, (2) analysing requirements, (3) examining data, (4) defining business processes, (5) implementing solutions, (6) conducting tests, and (7) disseminating results.

The testing methodology follows an interactive approach, directly engaging diverse user groups playing different roles in aUPaEU acceleration services, representing various stakeholder categories defined in D7.1.

The main objectives of WP6 are:

- Test the acceleration services developed in WP2 and WP5 with the identified groups of users.
- Validate the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) of the Agora of acceleration services, assessing whether the user experience, accessibility, and key features align with the needs of higher education institutions (HEIs) and their stakeholders.
- Track how the developed services support users' progress in the selected transformation area, contributing to institutional transformation toward universities of the future. Additionally, assess their advancement in implementing the prioritized areas of the transformation agenda. These efforts focus on six key aspects of HEI transformation: capacity, infrastructure, and resource sharing; researcher career attractiveness; collaboration with R&I ecosystem actors; open science; societal outreach; and gender equality.

The expected impact of WP6's activities is to validate the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) providing user feedback to refine and scale it into a fully developed Viable Solution (VS). The insights gained will strengthen institutional transformation strategies and support long-term adoption, ensuring the platform and services are impactful and scalable.

Indeed, the testing outcomes will play a critical role in refining the acceleration services and ensuring their alignment with the needs of higher education institutions (HEIs). The insights gathered will identify potential improvements in the services, assessing how well they meet users' needs and expectations. The results will highlight usability issues, adoption barriers, and areas requiring design adjustments, contributing to a more seamless user experience and ensuring that the platform is easy to use, accessible, and effective.

Moreover, the testing will provide a clear assessment of how the acceleration services contribute to institutional transformation, including their impact on processes, decision-making, and stakeholder engagement within HEIs. By evaluating the services' influence on key areas such as capacity building, collaboration, open science, and gender equality, we will be able to determine whether the services are effectively supporting HEIs in achieving their transformation agendas.

The outcomes of these tests will not only shape the evolution of the services and platform but will also guide the strategic direction of the project. As such, they will have a broader impact, influencing the work of other work packages (WPs) and contributing to the overall development and scaling of the Agora platform. This iterative feedback loop will ensure that the services remain relevant, effective, and adaptable to the evolving needs of HEIs, thus fostering long-term adoption and success.

The results of the tests will be documented through comprehensive reports, offering detailed feedback on the services evaluated within the Acceleration service catalogue. Our operational plan adopts a structured approach that involves dividing the testing process into three testing cycles, each targeting different macro-categories of stakeholders. In each cycle we will involve different roles, determined in WP4 business processes, from the same macro-category of stakeholders. In the initial testing cycles, we will engage users from core stakeholders, including Unite! and EPICUR. Subsequently, we will expand our focus to include those from extended stakeholders, such as other University Alliances for whose we are developing new Agoras.

In comparison with the previous deliverable **D6.1**, this document incorporates several key additions. First, the specific objectives of the testing activities are clearly defined, focusing on four main areas: (1) initial validation of problem-solution fit, (2) market validation, (3) usability and platform design validation, and (4) assessment of institutional transformation. Additionally, we have outlined the process for testing a new acceleration service and explained how testing activities are integrated throughout the key phases of the Design Thinking Approach, rather than being at a standalone stage.

This report also includes more detailed information about the testing methodology, such as the protocols for interviews and focus groups, ensuring transparency and replicability of the research process. Additionally, preliminary results from the first set of interviews have been incorporated, providing early insights into user needs, expectations, and initial reactions to the services tested. These findings serve as a foundation for further analysis and will help refine the approach for subsequent research phases.

2 Testing objectives and process

The objective of WP6 is the validation of both the individual acceleration services and the overall Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) of the Agora platform. **Section 2.1** outlines the specific objectives we aim to achieve through the testing activities. Given that the Agora platform features multiple services, which will be designed, developed, and added to the service catalogue incrementally, **Section 2.2** explains how the testing activities fit into the process of creating a new acceleration service.

2.1 Objectives

The testing activities aim to evaluate the acceleration services and the Agora platform, ensuring their functionality, usability, and effectiveness in driving institutional transformation within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This process will provide insights that help refine the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) and expand it into a fully functional Viable Solution (VS).

The testing activities will focus on the following objectives:

- **Initial validation of Problem-Solution Fit:** This test aims to evaluate whether the acceleration services effectively meet users' needs. By gathering feedback on the services' relevance, applicability, and perceived value, we determine if the solution addresses a significant problem for the target audience. This process assesses whether the acceleration services are tailored to meet the specific demands of HEIs and address real issues within the context of institutional transformation.
- **Market Validation:** The goal is to ensure that the acceleration services and the Agora platform align with broader market needs, as well as user's expectations and satisfaction. By evaluating how well the services meet these needs after implementation, we ensure that they are not only relevant for the target users but also have the potential to scale and be adopted by a larger audience.
- **Usability and Platform Design Validation:** This objective assesses the ease of use, and integration of the Agora platform, ensuring that users can efficiently navigate its functionalities and access the resources they need. Usability is a critical aspect of the testing process, as it directly impacts user experience and the platform's overall effectiveness. Ensuring that the platform is user-friendly, accessible, and well-integrated is key to encouraging engagement, adoption, and long-term use. The focus on usability will evaluate how easily users can interact with the platform, access the services and resources, and complete potential tasks without unnecessary obstacles.
- **Assessment of the Institutional Transformation:** This objective aims to monitor how the acceleration services support HEIs in implementing their transformation agendas. We will focus on key areas such as capacity building, resource sharing, research collaboration, open science, societal engagement, and gender equality. The testing will assess whether the services have a measurable impact on overcoming barriers to transformation and whether they effectively assist HEIs in achieving their institutional goals.

To achieve these objectives, the testing process follows a dual approach, evaluating both the acceleration services and the Agora platform:

- **Acceleration services testing:** structured testing activities will assess the effectiveness of individual acceleration services, ensuring they meet the diverse needs and expectations of different user groups. The composition of user groups will be dynamically defined based on the nature of each service, allowing for targeted feedback collection.
- **Platform testing:** In parallel, the Agora platform will undergo systematic testing focused on both technical development and usability. Key aspects of evaluation include the relevance and accuracy of stored information, the efficiency of information retrieval and search functionalities, and the overall user experience. These tests will ensure that the platform functions effectively and also meets the expectations of its diverse user base.

This comprehensive testing framework will provide valuable insights into the functionality, usability, and impact of both the acceleration services and the Agora platform, ensuring they effectively support HEI transformation and user engagement.

2.2 Planned testing process

The testing of a new acceleration service follows a structured process aligned with Design Thinking principles (Section 5 of D2.1), which consists of seven key phases, each playing a crucial role in the continuous improvement and evolution of acceleration services (see Table 2.1). The ultimate goal is to meet stakeholder requirements and drive innovation within the higher education sector.

Testing activities are integrated throughout the key phases of the Design Thinking Approach rather than being a standalone stage. They provide continuous feedback, ensuring an interactive and adaptive process. Specifically, testing is designed to validate the **MVS** of the Agora and generate valuable insights for its scaling to the **VS**. This strategy enables a dynamic and flexible approach, where iterative testing consistently assesses the effectiveness of acceleration services in both platform implementation and process execution. By aligning with users' evolving needs, it fosters ongoing innovation within the higher education ecosystem.

Table 2.1. Five Design Thinking Phases with Corresponding Steps in aUPaEU methodology

Design Thinking	Corresponding Step
Empathise	Step 1: Stakeholder engagement and awareness building (all) Step 2: Requirement analysis and service design (WP2) Step 7: Dissemination (WP7)
Define	Step 3: Data analysis (WP3) Step 4: Business process definition (WP4)
Ideate	Step 5: Implementation (WP5)
Prototype	Step 5: Implementation (WP5)
Test	Step 6: Testing and assessment (WP6)

2.2.1 Testing target

aUPaEU's approach to developing new acceleration services for alliances focuses on customization and co-creation, ensuring that each service is tailored to the specific needs of the Alliances. Stakeholders from the Alliances for which we are developing an Agora have been instrumental in the early stages of service development, making their involvement essential to the testing process.

We refer to these individuals as "**co-creators**" to distinguish them from other user groups involved in testing, which are:

- **Potential Users:** individuals who fit the target user profile of the service, including researchers, administrative staff, and PhD students within universities. Their feedback helps us understand their needs and challenges.
- **Current Users:** Those who are already utilising the implemented services and can provide insights into their experience, identifying areas for improvement and further refinement.

For more details about the stakeholders involved in the testing activities, see Section 2.3.

2.2.2 Process for Testing a New Acceleration Service

In this section, we outline how testing activities are systematically integrated into the key phases of the Design Thinking Approach for developing a new acceleration service. To provide a structured overview, Table 2.2 presents the evaluation stages embedded in the service development process. This testing framework, applied to each acceleration service created within the project, details the key objectives, methods, participant groups, timing, and expected outcomes of each phase. By following a user-centered approach, these activities ensure rigorous validation at multiple levels—from initial concept assessment to usability testing and long-term institutional impact evaluation.

As shown in the Table 2.2, we begin our testing activities during the third phase of the Design Thinking process, called "**Ideate**", when the new service is integrated into the platform. This stage is crucial to ensure that the service aligns with the actual needs of its intended users before moving forward with broader adoption. At this stage, initial interviews with co-creators are conducted to assess the problem-solution fit. The decision to begin testing with co-creators is driven by their deep knowledge of the service's design and objectives. The goal is to verify whether the service effectively addresses the original problem or if modifications are needed due to evolving user needs. Specifically, these interviews aim to:

- **Confirm the relevance of the solution:** Does it align with the initial needs identified during the design phase?
- **Identify missing features:** Are there additional functionalities that co-creators consider necessary?
- **Refine service requirements:** Feedback collected during these interviews helps improve the service and adapt it before further testing.

To enable meaningful feedback, co-creators will be trained through individual sessions focused on the technical functionalities of the service, allowing them to interact with the platform and test key features by performing relevant tasks. This hands-on approach ensures that co-creators can provide detailed insights into usability and potential improvements.

Table 2.2 Testing and evaluation activities for service development

Goal	Type of action test	Participant	Timing	Outcome
Initial validation	interview	Co-creators	After ideation	Confirm the relevance of the solution to address the initial problem, potential improvements
Market validation	Interview	Potential users	During service prototyping	Assessment of alignment with user needs, perceived value, and potential adoption barriers
Heuristic evaluation	Expert review	IT staff	During service prototyping	Identification of usability issues, design flaws, and areas for improvement based on UX principles.
Usability testing	Usability testing	Potential & current users	After prototype and users have started using the service	Detection of usability pain points, user behaviour insights, and actionable refinements to improve user experience.
Market validation	Interview	Current users	After prototype and users have started using the service	Insights from practical application, feedback on service effectiveness
Assessment of the institutional transformation	Focus group	key institutional stakeholders	An initial assessment after adoption by institutions and a follow-up after a defined period	Evaluation of service impact on institutional processes, decision-making, and stakeholder engagement.
Assessment of the institutional transformation	Survey delivery	key institutional stakeholders	An initial assessment after adoption by institutions and a follow-up after a defined period	Quantitative evaluation of service impact on institutional processes, decision-making, and stakeholder engagement.

In parallel with the co-creators interviews, we prepare heuristic evaluation with IT professionals who have experience on usability and user interface design. This step is useful to identify potential usability issues before they become deeply embedded in the design.

The heuristic evaluation phase focuses on several key aspects:

- **Workflow efficiency:** Evaluating whether key user tasks can be completed efficiently without unnecessary complexity.
- **Navigation and interface responsiveness:** Ensuring that menus, buttons, and interactive elements are intuitive and user-friendly.
- **Error handling and system feedback:** Testing how the platform responds to user input, including error messages and system notifications.

Once feedback from co-creators and IT staff has been incorporated, the service advances to the "**Prototype**" phase, where it is refined and prepared for broader implementation. At this stage, the service is considered more mature and is introduced to potential users through targeted promotion and coaching activities to encourage adoption. This is where the content from Agora Support (agora.widening.eu) plays a key role. Agora Support, launched in January 2025, is a newly developed platform designed to provide support materials to new alliances that aUPaEU introduces to Agora.

To ensure the service is not only functional but also truly valuable to end users, we conduct a new round of testing to evaluate its **market-solution fit**. This involves **engaging both potential users**—who could benefit from the platform’s services—and **current users**, gathering insights into their experiences, expectations, and any remaining areas for improvement. In particular, we conduct interviews distinguishing between potential and current users, as their perspectives and contributions are significantly different.

- **Current users** provide firsthand insights based on their direct experience with the service, offering valuable feedback on its usability, effectiveness, and areas for improvement. Their input helps refine and optimize the service to better meet their needs.
- **Potential users**, on the other hand, help assess the service’s appeal, relevance, and accessibility for newcomers. Their feedback is crucial for identifying potential barriers to adoption and ensuring the service effectively attracts and engages new users.

By incorporating both perspectives, the testing process ensures that the acceleration service remains both functional for existing users and accessible to future ones. We plan to first interview potential users during the prototyping phase to gather early insights. Once the prototype is developed and actively used, we will shift our focus to current users, collecting feedback in this more advanced stage to refine and optimize the service based on real user experiences.

After developing the prototype, we will conduct Usability Testing with real or representative users. These activities focus on improving the interface, functionality, and overall user experience, ensuring seamless and intuitive interaction with the platform. The sessions are designed to identify usability issues and address the specific needs of target users, particularly those with limited experience using digital tools and online platforms. The service will be

tested alongside the platform, including other services, to ensure full integration and a cohesive user experience.

Lastly, the final step is to evaluate the impact of the service, alongside the platform, in driving institutional transformation. This evaluation will take place once the service has been adopted by a sufficient number of users, following the validation of specific Agora services and the implementation of usability enhancements, ensuring a thorough review of their effectiveness. The specific goal is to measure how well each service supports HEIs in overcoming barriers to institutional transformation. To assess this impact, we will use:

- **Focus Groups:** Engage Alliance members to gather in-depth feedback and insights.
- **Targeted Survey:** Assess user perceptions and measure the platform's impact on institutional transformation.

By gathering continuous feedback and refining the service through these iterative steps, we ensure that the Agora platform remains responsive to the needs of its users and aligned with the broader goals of institutional transformation.

2.3 Stakeholders and users involved in the process

The planned tests involve users belonging to different macro-categories of stakeholders, as defined in D7.1 and in D7.2. During testing, we specifically target co-creators as well as current and prospective users of the aUPaEU acceleration services. These users are drawn from university alliances, individual HEIs, and research institutions—whether or not they are part of an alliance—that are involved in the co-creation of the Agora platform, following the design thinking approach.

The selection criteria are based on their role within the acceleration services and their institutional affiliations. The primary categories include:

- **Core stakeholders:** universities belonging to the European Alliances Unite! and EPICUR, and that are either direct or indirect beneficiaries of the aUPaEU project (see D7.1)
- **Extended stakeholders:** As outlined in D7.1, this group includes citizens, higher education institutions (HEIs) and research organizations, university alliances, networks of HEIs and research institutions, public administrations, and industry/businesses. Within this group, we will specifically target the subcategory of **"Allies"** (see D7.2)—stakeholders such as alliances and consortia of universities that have already expressed interest in receiving a tailored version of the Agora platform and in co-creating its acceleration services with us. Once these Allies are actively involved in the co-design of the services and the Agora platform, they will transition into core aUPaEU stakeholders and will be invited to participate in the testing activities. Additional

subcategories within the extended stakeholder may be invited at a later stage of testing, particularly if they become involved in the future development of new services tailored to their needs.

- **Widening area stakeholders:** Institutions in the Widening area

Participants are selected based on their institutional involvement in acceleration services, their engagement in institutional transformation activities, and their willingness to provide feedback during the testing phases. The recruitment strategy leverages:

- Direct invitations through established networks from previous WP activities.
- Open calls within university alliances and research institutions.
- Targeted outreach to institutions in the Widening area to ensure diverse representation.

Participants engage in:

- Testing specific acceleration services relevant to their institutional needs.
- Providing usability feedback on the Agora platform.
- Participating in surveys, interviews, and focus groups to assess the impact of acceleration services on institutional transformation.

The expected number of participants varies per test cycle, ensuring diverse representation across different roles and institutions.

We continuously validate the acceleration services from both platform and process implementation perspectives. In each testing session, user groups evaluate a selection of services from the catalogue, allowing for iterative assessment and refinement. Throughout this process, we also closely monitor progress in the designated transformation area.

Each testing group will be composed of users with different roles within the same macro-category of stakeholders. These roles are defined based on the business processes identified from WP4 in the deliverable D4.1 “Inventory, Action Plan and preliminary set of Business Processes”. This approach ensures that testing reflects the diverse perspectives and interactions within each stakeholder group, providing a comprehensive evaluation of how the acceleration services function in real-world scenarios.

Administrative and technical staff

These individuals provide essential administrative and strategic support for research activities within universities. This group includes professionals responsible for the operational and technical management of services within HEIs. Depending on the service’s theme and functionality, we engage individuals from the relevant administrative or technical units. Their feedback is vital for assessing the usability of the solution as well as its seamless integration into existing institutional processes. Whether using the service directly or overseeing its

management, these stakeholders evaluate how effectively the solution supports institutional workflows, ensures regulatory compliance, and enhances the efficiency of administrative tasks. Additionally, they play a critical role in the solution's implementation, maintenance, and ongoing support.

Academic staff

This group includes individuals actively conducting research in HEIs. They test how well the solution fits into their daily workflows and meets their research needs. Key considerations include:

- **Early-Career Researchers** (Postdocs, Junior Faculty): They often balance research with teaching and grant applications. Their input will highlight usability for those new to administrative processes.
- **Senior Faculty**: They lead research projects, secure funding, and supervise teams. They can assess how the solution supports project management, funding acquisition, and collaboration.

Students

Advanced students (e.g., final year Master's students, PhD students) who are preparing to transition from education to a research career. Their involvement helps test the solution's relevance for students pursuing research paths. They can provide insights into:

- Training and skill development needs.
- Ease of use for those new to research administration.
- How well the services prepare them for future research roles.

2.3.1 Universities involved in the testing activities

Since aUPaEU brings together two Alliances, EPICUR and Unite!, we reached out to both Alliances in order to raise awareness for our project, establish channels of communications, and explore areas of collaboration.

Being core stakeholders for our project (see D7.1, section "3.3. The stakeholders mapping classification"), the universities of the Unite! and EPICUR Alliances are considered as main users for our tests. In addition to these, we will also involve universities that are part of other alliances or consortia and have already expressed interest in receiving a tailored version of the Agora platform and in co-creating its acceleration services with us.

Currently, eight alliances or projects have either already integrated or are in discussions to incorporate Agora into their initiatives. Since the pace of their deployment may vary, the exact timing of their involvement in the testing cannot be determined at this stage, our final goal is

to engage at least 20 universities across 4 different alliances. The testing user groups will consist of individuals from these universities.

Universities partner of the project

Universities that are project partners are involved in the initial tests. This allows us to verify the effectiveness of the testing tasks and provides us with insights to improve our approach when conducting tests with users from other universities. Specifically, we plan to engage the users who are not directly involved in the project. Yet, involving first partner universities ensures faster coordination and facilitates test participation while the services and Agora are still in the preliminary stages.

The project partner universities are:

- Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań (AMU)
- Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
- Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble (INP-UGA)
- Politecnico di Torino (PoliTO)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)

Universities within Unite! Alliance

[Unite! – University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering](#) is a strategic, agile and dynamic Alliance of nine European Universities based on shared values, vision and trust. It aims to be a driving force for technology and innovation, a multilingual transeuropean campus training the future experts of digital and green transition.

Unite! Alliance has been defined as a core stakeholder since it is directly connected with aUPaEU (see D7.1) and its associated stakeholders are the actual users of Agora.

Universities within EPiCUR Alliance

[EPiCUR - the European University Alliance](#) belongs to the first generation of European Alliances. It gathers nine partner Universities committed to pilot a new way of intensifying collaboration among Higher Education institutions through the creation of a European University.

EPiCUR Alliance has been defined as a core stakeholder since it is directly connected with aUPaEU (see D7.1). However, it is important to note that only specific universities—KIT, AMU, UniStra—are currently involved in testing the EPiCUR Agora, and this will be focused primarily on the research infrastructure acceleration service.

Universities involved in the Sister Projects

Within the extended stakeholders, aUPaEU invites individuals [Accelerate Future HEI](#) project as users, since we have established a fruitful collaborative relationship and they are key stakeholders to assess the impact of acceleration services.

aUPaEU considers the CATALISI project and Accelerate Future HEI as sister projects because all projects received funding through the same call, HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-51, and we share values and objectives to improve Higher Education Institutions.

The connection with CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI was first established in May 2023 for a training session workshop, “Acceleration Services in support of the transformation of Higher Education Institutions”, organised by NPC WIDERA. During the following months the projects’ communication personnel developed a collaborative relationship, outlining communication actions to be taken jointly. This collaboration expanded to other aspects, such as writing a joint policy brief report. The aUPaEU project is determined to continue this fruitful cooperation in the future and to make joint progress towards acceleration services for universities.

Universities from New Alliances for Agora Development

Other alliances have also been involved in the development of Agora platforms, expanding the scope of testing and service evaluation across various university networks. For example, the most advanced collaboration is at the moment with Eu Green Alliance and CIVIS Alliance.

[EU GREEN](#) is an Alliance of nine European universities, spanning a wide geographical area (from Sweden to Portugal and from the northwest of Ireland to Romania). These institutions have entered into an agreement to evolve, in the long term, into a single European University where students, faculty, and administrative staff can move freely between campuses to attend lectures, teach, participate in training programs, and engage in sports, cultural activities, and more.

[CIVIS](#) is a European Civic University Alliance formed by the alliance of 11 leading European research higher education institutions. Rooted in their urban and regional landscape, CIVIS member universities actively contribute to the social, cultural and economic dynamism of their ecosystem and promote European values such as inclusiveness, gender equality, non-discrimination and social equity. CIVIS will forge richer interactions and co-creation of knowledge and skills with citizens, schools, enterprises, social and cultural associations.

3 Testing Methodology

In the previous section, we outlined the testing process for a new service, offering an overview of the actions and activities we will undertake to apply the methodology in a practical context. In this chapter, we delve into the testing methodology itself, detailing the theoretical principles that underpin our approach and the specific methods we employ—such as interviews, focus groups, and surveys. Hence, the purpose of this section is to present the principles that underpin our testing strategy, ensuring that each service meets user needs while also being scalable to a Validated Solution (VS).

Our testing methodology is designed to systematically evaluate the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) of Agora, with an emphasis on gathering targeted insights from diverse user groups at various stages of service development. Through iterative testing of acceleration services from the Agora catalogue, participants will assess both platform functionality and process execution. Continuous feedback from these groups will be essential for refining service functionalities, improving user experience, and ensuring alignment with stakeholder expectations. The composition of testing groups will be carefully selected to reflect the unique characteristics and demographics of the users relevant to each service.

As outlined in the previous section, the methodology includes distinct activities based on the stage of service development and adoption. This section details the approaches used to assess the effectiveness and impact of our acceleration services, aligned with key testing objectives such as Initial Validation of Problem-Solution Fit, Market Validation, Usability and Platform Design Validation, and Assessment of Institutional Transformation. This nuanced testing strategy aims to provide comprehensive insights into the functionality, usability, and effectiveness of both individual services and the overarching platform.

Finally, to ensure the ethical collection and use of data, we will obtain informed consent from all participants. Written information will be provided to participants prior to their involvement, and we will process all data in compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant legal and ethical standards. All research data will be managed in a FAIR manner, as detailed in the Data Management Plan (D1.1).

3.1 Initial Validation of Problem-solution fit

The first stage of our testing methodology focuses on validating the Problem-Solution Fit through direct engagement **with co-creators**. To achieve this, we will conduct one-on-one interviews with selected users who have been actively involved in the early stages of service development. These interviews will focus on evaluating whether the service effectively addresses a significant and relevant problem for its target audience.

Our primary objectives are:

- To validate whether the originally identified problem remains relevant and significant to co-creators.
- To assess how well the current solution meets the targeted needs.
- To gather qualitative insights to refine the service based on user expertise and feedback.

By leveraging the experience of co-creators, we will ensure that the service evolves in alignment with actual user expectations and requirements. Their insights will help refine the service's value proposition, usability, and implementation strategy.

3.1.1 Interviews

Interviews are a technique consisting of a specific type of conversation, structured and guided by a researcher who intends to stimulate certain information to access other observations. Qualitative and quantitative interviews differ in the structure of the conversation: more or less open, in the more or less importance given to the interviewee's opinion, and in the more or less prevalent creativity of the interviewer. Qualitative interviews are beneficial when one wants to analyse the meaning individuals give to the object of inquiry and their participation. Despite the interviewee answering questions, a conversation and an unspoken relationship develop with the interviewer, and the latter is necessarily an active participant.

The goal is to validate the results of WP5 (reported in the Deliverables D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3) and provide feedback to WP2 and WP4 on the catalogue of services. Therefore, we will focus on verifying whether the services meet their needs and assessing if the solution effectively and efficiently addresses them. The idea is that interview subjects will validate—or not validate—assumptions we made earlier in the development process. Hence, we will present the services to the users and get their feedback.

The results of these interviews are communicated to the other WPs. The outcome determines whether the design concept and business process effectively meet user satisfaction or require refinement to appeal to our potential users.

The interviews are semi-structured to gather data from the respondents in a structured way with open-ended discussion. Each interview will be about one 45-60 minutes in length. We will plan for 3-5 interviews with co-creators for each service. Since co-creators are deeply familiar with the service's design and objectives, the goal is not quantity, but depth of insight. A smaller number of interviews ensures that we can gather rich, focused feedback without overwhelming the process, and it allows us to capture any key challenges or blind spots in the service development before engaging a wider audience.

All interviews will be conducted remotely, using the Microsoft Teams platform. This allows for flexible scheduling, making it easier to engage with participants from different locations while maintaining an efficient and accessible process. The remote format also facilitates a

comfortable and focused environment for participants to provide honest and detailed feedback.

The interviews will be recorded (with participant consent) for later transcription, and qualitative content analysis.

Since the number of co-creators is limited, the goal is to capture all relevant insights and highlight key feedback. Content analysis will be particularly useful for identifying the key themes, challenges, and insights from each co-creator. Instead of relying on a rigid thematic coding process, we will allow the data to emerge organically, identifying broad patterns as well as specific areas of interest. We will focus on meaningful interpretation rather than simply identifying patterns. As co-creator are closely involved with the services, the feedback will likely be more technical and in-depth, so interpretation is key to distilling actionable insights. Hence, the analysis will focus on in-depth interpretation, cross-case comparisons, and prioritizing actionable insights.

3.1.1.1 Interview Protocol Steps

The interviews will follow a structured process to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The key steps include:

1. **Participant Selection:** Identify and recruit individuals actively involved in the early stages of service development or those who provided user requirements for the specific service.
2. **Interview Invitation:** Send an invitation email outlining the interview's purpose, estimated duration, and confidentiality terms.
3. **Follow-up Reminder:** If no response is received within a week, send a follow-up email.
4. **Confirmation & Pre-Interview Materials:** Upon acceptance, provide the interview guide and schedule the session. Send a calendar invite to confirm the date and time.
5. **Interview Execution:**
 - a. Obtain participant consent to record the session (or take detailed notes if they decline).
 - b. Conduct the interview following the semi-structured format, ensuring all key topics are covered while allowing room for open-ended discussion.
6. **Post-Interview Processing:**
 - a. Transcribe the interview in English.
 - b. Code and analyse the data for qualitative insights.
 - c. Share key findings with relevant work packages (WP5, WP2, and WP4) for service refinement, as described in Section 3.5 "Feedback Loop".

Each interview will follow a structured but flexible format to maintain consistency while allowing participants to express their views freely.

1. Introduction (5 minutes):

- Briefly introduce the interviewer and the project.
- Explain the interview's purpose and expected outcomes.
- Request permission to record the conversation.
- Ask participants to briefly introduce themselves.

2. Service Introduction (5 minutes) -skippable:

- Ask if the participant is familiar with the current implementation of the service. If not, provide a brief overview of the implemented service.

1. Interview Questions (25 minutes):

- Follow the interview guide (see Appendix 8.1), allowing for follow-up questions where relevant.

2. Closing (5 minutes):

- Summarise the key points discussed.
- Thank the participants for their time and valuable feedback.
- Provide information on how their feedback will contribute to service improvements.
- Offer to share updates on future developments.

The interview will follow a structured guideline, which is provided in the appendix of this document. The questions aim to explore the service's origin, effectiveness, and potential improvements.

3.2 Market validation

To validate our services, we will engage both **potential and current users**. The primary objective is to assess Market-Solution Fit—determining whether our solution effectively addresses the needs of a well-defined market. This validation confirms that the solution is not only viable but also appealing to the target segment, driving adoption and engagement.

1. **There is clear demand** – The target audience recognizes the problem and is actively looking for a solution.
2. **The solution effectively addresses the problem** – Users find the service valuable, and it resolves their challenges better than existing alternatives.
3. **There is willingness to adopt** – Potential customers are ready to integrate the solution into their workflows and, ideally, pay for it.

To achieve this, we will gather qualitative insights through Semi-structured interviews, providing an in-depth understanding of individual user experiences, pain points, and service expectations while maintaining a structured framework.

Each interview focuses on a specific service, enabling us to assess service adoption, user satisfaction, and alignment with market needs. The findings will guide strategic improvements, ensuring our services remain relevant, valuable, and widely adopted.

3.2.1 Interviews

We will conduct **semi-structured interviews** targeting **both potential** (or prospective) and **current users** to assess the effectiveness and relevance of our services. Potential users are the individuals who fit the profile of the intended users but have yet to adopt the services. Engaging with them is crucial to understanding their needs, preferences, and potential barriers to adoption. These insights will help refine our offering and evaluate the anticipated impact of the developed service on their daily workflows. On the other hand, current users are individuals who are already utilizing Agora's services. Their feedback is critical for identifying pain points, unmet needs, and areas for improvement. Involving them allows us to assess the actual impact of the services on their workflows and processes, providing valuable input for optimizing functionality and user experience. Additionally, understanding how our service compares to alternative solutions will help ensure its continued relevance and engagement.

The findings from these interviews will be shared with other WPs to inform decision-making and service refinement. The results will determine whether the implemented service effectively meets user needs or requires adjustments to enhance adoption and usability. These findings will be reported in Deliverable D6.3, which will provide a comprehensive report on the testing of the Viable Solution (VS) of the Agora acceleration services with user groups, evaluating the received feedback and assessing the progress in the institutional transformation areas

To ensure a structured yet flexible approach, we will use semi-structured interviews that combine a predefined framework with open-ended discussions, allowing participants to express their perspectives freely. Each interview will be about one 30-45 minutes in length. It is commonly recommended to conduct at least 5-10 customer validation interviews. However, the advice also emphasises continuing until recurring themes emerge. Consequently, we have not yet set a definitive number of interviews for each service, recognizing that the required quantity may vary based on the service's complexity. As a result, we have established a minimum threshold of 5 interviews for each service. After these initial interviews, we will refine our assumptions and questions based on the insights gained. If no new insights arise, we conclude the interview process for that service. Given that we will also be organizing focus groups, these interviews will be complementary, providing more granular insights into individual user experiences and validating the findings from group discussions.

All interviews will be conducted remotely, using the Microsoft Teams platform. This allows for flexible scheduling, making it easier to engage with participants from different locations while maintaining an efficient and accessible process. The remote format also facilitates a comfortable and focused environment for participants to provide honest and detailed feedback.

The interviews will be recorded (with participant consent) for later transcription, coding, and qualitative content analysis.

The interview results will be triangulated with findings from the focus groups. This means we will cross-check and compare insights from the interviews with those from the focus groups to validate key points. This process will help ensure that the feedback gathered is consistent and reliable, giving us a more comprehensive understanding of user needs and perceptions.

After synthesizing the results, we will extract actionable insights to inform future service iterations. These insights will be aligned with the testing objectives, such as improving usability, enhancing service features, and addressing market fit. A summary of key recommendations will be developed for each service, focusing on areas for improvement, potential new features, or changes in service delivery based on user feedback.

3.2.1.1 Interview Protocol

The interviews will be conducted using a structured process to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. These steps align with those outlined in Section 3.1.1.1, "Interview Protocol" regarding the problem-solution fit, with the key distinction that we will target potential users—individuals who match the profile of our target audience but have not yet engaged with our services. Hence, in this case the first step will involve identifying and recruiting individuals who are either already using at least one service on the Agora platform or who meet the criteria of intended users but have yet to adopt the services. Specifically, we focus on:

- Researchers
- Administrative staff
- PhD students within universities
- These individuals can provide valuable insights into their specific needs, challenges, and expectations, which will help us refine our services to ensure they effectively address real pain points.

We will identify and reach out to potential users through:

- Work package leaders
- Co-creators of the services
- Individuals met during public presentations of Agora
- Participants from events and conferences relevant to higher education and research

By leveraging these networks, we can engage individuals who are likely to benefit from the services but have not yet had the opportunity to test them.

Instead, Current users are individuals who are actively utilizing our services. They represent the primary group for evaluating the effectiveness and market acceptance of our solution. To systematically engage with current users, we will:

- Generate a comprehensive list of individuals currently using our services
- Segment users based on service type and demographics to ensure diverse representation in the study

The goal of engaging with current users is to assess the Product-Market Fit, determining how well the service meets their needs and expectations. We will explore:

- How effectively the service addresses their challenges
- The perceived value and impact on their workflows
- Comparison with alternative solutions
- Areas requiring improvement
- Long-term adoption potential

Interview structure and guideline will have slight variations depending on whether the interviewee is a potential or current user.

The following is the interview structure targeting potential users:

1. Introduction (5 minutes):

- Briefly introduce the interviewer and the project.
- Explain the interview's purpose and expected outcomes.
- Request permission to record the conversation.
- Ask participants to briefly introduce themselves.

2. Service Introduction (5 minutes):

- Provide a concise overview of the new services.
- Highlight key features, benefits, and unique selling points.
- Provide a live demonstration of the service on the platform, showcasing its location and functionality to enhance understanding.

3. Interview Questions (25 minutes):

- Follow the interview guide (see Appendix 8.2), allowing for follow-up questions where relevant.

4. Closing (5 minutes):

- Summarize the key points discussed.
- Thank the participants for their time and valuable feedback.
- Provide information on how their feedback will contribute to service improvements.
- Offer to share updates on future developments.

Instead, the interview structure outlined below is specifically designed for current users:

1. Introduction (5 minutes):

- Briefly introduce the interviewer and the project.
- Explain the interview's purpose and expected outcomes.

- Request permission to record the conversation.
- Ask participants to briefly introduce themselves.

2. Interview Questions (25 minutes):

- Follow the interview guide (see Appendix 8.3), allowing for follow-up questions where relevant.

3. Closing (5 minutes):

- Summarize the key points discussed.
- Thank the participants for their time and valuable feedback.
- Provide information on how their feedback will contribute to service improvements.
- Offer to share updates on future developments.

3.3 Usability testing and platform design

3.3.1 Evaluation Goal

Evaluation tests the usability, functionality, and acceptability of an interactive system. Since the Agora is meant to serve as a model for other alliances or networks of organisations, the testing process will be open to feedback from other alliances.

Evaluation is a crucial process that assesses the usability, functionality, and acceptability of an interactive system. When developing an evaluation task, several factors must be taken into consideration:

- The design stage, whether it's a sketch, prototype, or the final product.
- Initial goals set during the development process.
- Different dimensions and aspects of the system.
- Utilising a variety of techniques.

The goal of the evaluation of the platform's usability is to identify design problems in the user interface as soon as possible to fix them before proceeding with further development. It evaluates how easily users can interact with the platform, access the services and resources, and complete potential tasks without unnecessary obstacles, thus ensuring that users can efficiently navigate its functionalities and access the resources they need.

This part of the evaluation is conducted in three ways: 1) an initial heuristic evaluation with IT professionals to identify usability problems in the user interface of Agora, 2) a usability testing session with real or representative users of Agora, and 3) a structured customer satisfaction survey.

3.3.2 Heuristic Evaluation

Heuristic evaluation is a usability inspection method conducted by experts, where evaluators use well-known high-level guidelines or principles (i.e., heuristics) to measure the usability of user interfaces in independent walkthroughs and report any issues. Evaluators, in this way, reveal insights that can help design and development teams enhance the usability of a product or system in various stages of realization.

It is important to note that heuristic evaluations cannot replace user research (e.g., a usability evaluation), since user experience design is highly contextual. Good experiences require testing the design with real or realistic users. Nonetheless, heuristic evaluations can complement such work, as in this specific case. We are, indeed, conducting a heuristic evaluation in preparation for a usability test (“Prototype” phase) to identify the main issues in the design that can be fixed and the areas or tasks to carefully consider during testing.

A heuristic evaluation is composed of four main steps:

1. Select a Set of Suitable Heuristics.
2. Prepare for the Heuristic Evaluation.
3. Evaluate Independently.
4. Consolidate Identified Issues and Report Back.

Each step is described and contextualized for the Agora services in the following paragraphs, while each session is expected to last between 1 and 2 hours.

Step 1. Select a Set of Heuristics

While a heuristic evaluation can be conducted with any set of heuristics, to assess general usability, we will use Jakob Nielsen’s 10 usability heuristics, summarized below. These heuristics were developed in 1990 and are widely used as a reliable set of principles. They are based on an understanding of human behavior, psychology, and information processing, thus providing a solid foundation for the evaluation purpose.

The adopted heuristics are:

1. Visibility of System Status
2. Match Between the System and the Real World
3. User Control and Freedom
4. Consistency and Standards
5. Error Prevention
6. Recognition Rather than Recall
7. Flexibility and Efficiency of Use
8. Aesthetic and Minimalist Design
9. Help Users Recognize, Diagnose, and Recover from Errors

10. Help and Documentation

A detailed description of each heuristic, together with possible examples, are available on the Nielsen-Norman Group website: <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ten-usability-heuristics/>.

Step 2. Prepare for the Heuristic Evaluation

It has been demonstrated that heuristic evaluations work best when performed by more than one individual, typically between three and five experts who work independently. This is because each evaluator – no matter how experienced or expert – is likely to miss some potential usability issues.

In our context, we are conducting the evaluation with three IT professionals who have conducted more than one heuristic evaluation in the past year and are more than familiar with the process and Nielsen’s heuristics. In addition to recruiting evaluators, the preparation includes providing each evaluator with the same information about the domain and the scenario to be evaluated. In our case, the evaluators will receive a set of tasks suitable for evaluating at least two acceleration services within the Agora platform.

Step 3. Evaluate Independently

With a set of tasks and knowledge about the two services under evaluation, each evaluator works independently from the others.

For each task, each evaluator steps through the design several times and inspects the various elements of the user interface (i.e., design elements, features, or decisions). During the inspection, the evaluator checks the design according to each heuristic. As such, the heuristics serve as a “reminder” of things to look for.

The evaluator conducts at least two steps for each acceleration service:

1. They get a general feeling for the interaction flow and overall scope of the Agora service under analysis.
2. They focus on specific user interface elements, understanding where they fit in the general picture and how they contribute to completing the assigned tasks.

The evaluator takes notes of the encountered issues in a dedicated workbook that will be provided. The workbook allows the evaluator to document each issue:

1. *Which* heuristic it violates (e.g., heuristic #1).
2. *Where* the issue is located (e.g., a button or on multiple pages).
3. *Why* it is an issue.
4. A *severity rating* (from 1 – Cosmetic problem only, to 4 – Usability catastrophe).

These four pieces of information are fundamental for the design or development team to gain a deep understanding of the issues and address them accordingly.

In particular, the reasoning behind the identified violations is crucial for understanding the evaluator's perspective and making appropriate modifications to the user interface. The severity rating, on the other hand, provides valuable information for prioritizing resources to fix the most serious problems. Severity is determined by a combination of factors: the frequency with which the problem occurs, the impact of the problem if it occurs, and its persistence. If the evaluator notices any design issues not specifically related to a heuristic, they can report them in the workbook as a "non-heuristic violation," filling out all the remaining points.

Step 4. Consolidate Identified Issues and Report Back

After each evaluator completes their evaluation, they meet and discuss the identified violations. The goal is to provide a single list for the design and development team.

Consequently, starting from the individual workbooks, the evaluators create a unified list of violations, merging them in case of duplications. Since severity ratings from a single evaluator have been found to be unreliable, they agree on a consensus ranking for all the identified issues, for example, by computing the average of their ratings in the case of duplicate violations. If the evaluators decide to dismiss a violation, they can mark it with a severity rating of zero (i.e., they do not agree that this is a usability problem at all). The final list of violations is then passed to the design and development teams, and the three evaluators remain available for a meeting to provide further clarifications.

3.3.3 Usability testing

The Nielsen-Norman Group defines usability testing in this way:

In a usability-testing session, a researcher (called a "facilitator" or a "moderator") asks a participant to perform tasks, usually using one or more specific user interfaces. While the participant completes each task, the researcher observes the participant's behaviour and listens for feedback.

Typically, the goal is to:

- Identify problems in the design,
- Uncovering opportunities to improve,
- Learning about the target user's behaviour and preferences.

As illustrated in Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2, the facilitator guides the participant through the test process, providing instructions, answering questions, and asking follow-up questions. Importantly, the facilitator should not influence the participants' behaviour.

Core Elements of Usability Testing

Figure 3.1: The core elements of Usability Testing

Usability Testing: Flow of Information

Figure 3.2: The flow of information in Usability Testing

Tasks

Tasks in a usability test are realistic activities that participants might perform in real life. For example: “Your printer is showing 'Error 5200.' How can you get rid of the error message?” Task instructions can be delivered verbally or in written form.

Participants

Participants in usability testing should be realistic users of the product or service being studied. They may already use the system and should be “similar” to the target user group. Consideration should be given to their background in computing, experience with the task, motivation, education, and ability with the natural language used in the interface.

Type of Usability Testing

Usability testing can be categorised as either qualitative or quantitative:

- Qualitative Usability Testing: This focuses on collecting insights, findings, and anecdotes about how people use the product or service.
- Quantitative Usability Testing: This concentrates on collecting metrics that describe the user experience, such as task success and time on task.

Usability testing can be conducted either in-person or remotely, providing flexibility in the evaluation process. Both approaches offer unique advantages, and the choice depends on the specific needs and constraints of the evaluation task.

In conclusion, a comprehensive evaluation process, including usability testing, is essential to ensure that an interactive system meets its intended goals and provides an optimal user experience. By identifying issues early and gathering valuable insights, developers can make informed decisions to enhance the overall quality of the system. Following the project’s Design Thinking approach, the results from these tests will support the activities of WP5 enhancing and assessing the minimum viable solution (MVS) to obtain a viable solution (VS).

3.3.3.1 Our Plan

In a Qualitative Usability Testing, we will collect insights, findings, and anecdotes about how people use the platform and the services. The target of these tests will be the actual users of those services. We will conduct qualitative usability tests remotely to allow testers to perform tasks with the services in their own natural settings. This approach enables testers to interact with the online services in environments that closely resemble real-world usage scenarios. The sessions will be moderated. By observing how users navigate the product and complete tasks in their natural environments, the moderator can get valuable insights into its usability and effectiveness. The outcomes of these tests will allow us to learn more about users' opinions and observe challenging or interesting points in their experience with the design of each service. Hence, the expected outcomes will include the identification of potential issues and

the collection of suggestions for a modification to the design for better performance. Because the object is to reveal these potential issues to the session's facilitator, it is not necessarily important how many participants experience the same issue; WP6 and WP5 (the designers) will use their expertise to judge which issues should be addressed. This remote testing method ensures greater authenticity and relevance to users' actual experiences, thereby enhancing the validity of our usability findings.

Jakob Nielsen (2000) provided guidance on usability testing sample sizes in his article "[Why You Only Need to Test with 5 Users](#)", suggesting that testing with 15 users is typically required to identify all usability issues in a design. However, he recommends an iterative approach, advising to conduct three tests with five users each. This method involves addressing the problems discovered in each test before proceeding to the next round of testing with a new group of five users. Testing the services on the platform with five users should allow us to find almost as many usability problems as we would find using many more test participants. Hence, we aim to have the platform, and its services undergo Qualitative Usability Testing at least three times throughout the duration of the project. Each session will involve 5 participants and will be 90-120 minutes long.

At the end of the session, we will ask participants to answer a satisfaction questionnaire (e.g., rating from 1 to 5: How much do you appreciate the final site? Is the platform intuitive? Is the navigation quick? Do you like the graphics? Is the Agora providing enough useful information for each service?). Moreover, the observations collected during the sessions may be augmented through the follow-up questionnaire.

3.3.4 Survey

Recognizing the importance of quantitative data in service evaluation, we will develop a structured customer satisfaction survey to systematically assess the acceleration services and validate the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS). The primary objective is to gather measurable insights into user experience, service effectiveness, and perceived impact, providing a data-driven foundation for continuous service refinement. The survey will be designed to measure key performance indicators (KPIs) and other relevant metrics aligned with the overarching goals of the service assessment. It will also assess the platform's development over time, ensuring continuous feedback to WP5, which oversees the prototyping of the MVS and its subsequent scaling to the full version.

The surveys will be administered remotely to users who have participated in focus groups, platform testing, and potentially in events or workshops where the Agora platform was presented. This targeted approach ensures that responses are gathered from individuals with direct experience using the services, enhancing the reliability and relevance of the data collected.

Users will be asked to evaluate various aspects using a Likert scale, ensuring consistency in quantitative analysis. Additionally, a set of quantifiable indicators will be established to benchmark service performance systematically. These indicators will be informed by literature reviews, expert consultations, and insights from previous qualitative testing phases. The survey will be structured into thematic sections to ensure a comprehensive analysis of user feedback:

- **Overall Platform User Experience and Usability:** This section will assess the ease of use, accessibility, and overall interaction with the Agora platform. Participants will be asked to evaluate the platform's intuitiveness, navigation clarity, ease of locating and selecting a service, understanding how to use the platform, and the adequacy of available support resources.
- **Specific Service Experience:** Users will rate each service individually based on its intuitiveness, design quality, technical functionality, and the suitability of its features. This will help identify areas where improvements may be needed in service implementation.
- **Perceived Value and Relevance:** This section will measure how well the services facilitate users' workflows and address their institutional needs. Respondents will be asked to identify the most useful services, assess whether these services effectively meet their needs, and evaluate their overall satisfaction with the solutions provided.
- **Optional Suggestions for Improvement:** An optional open-ended section will collect qualitative feedback on potential service enhancements, missing functionalities, and future development priorities, allowing users to share insights and suggestions for refining the platform and its offerings.

The survey results will play a crucial role in validating the acceleration services and refining the MVS. By analysing both qualitative and quantitative responses, we will identify actionable insights that guide iterative service improvements and ensure alignment with institutional transformation objectives.

3.4 Assessment of the institutional transformation

A key objective of WP6 is to monitor the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) as they progress towards the universities of the future, aligning their efforts with the European Research Area (ERA) agenda. This transformation is central to the aUPaEU project, which aims to accelerate these transitions through a variety of services delivered via a digital platform. These services foster collaboration and provide essential support to HEIs, university networks, and alliances in implementing the six key areas of the transformation

agenda: capacity, infrastructure, and resource sharing; researcher career attractiveness; collaboration with R&I ecosystem actors; open science; societal outreach; and gender equality.

To assess the institutional transformation and its alignment with the ERA agenda, we will employ focus groups with key stakeholders from HEIs. These focus groups will facilitate discussions on the challenges, successes, and progress in implementing the transformation agenda at an institutional level. They will provide valuable qualitative insights into the real-world impact of the services delivered via the digital platform, allowing us to understand how HEIs are navigating the six key areas.

In addition to focus groups, some interviews may be conducted to gain deeper insights from individuals directly involved in the transformation process. These interviews could allow us to capture more detailed feedback on specific aspects of the transformation and its alignment with the ERA agenda. Interviews will be particularly useful for understanding the nuances of institutional changes and for exploring specific case studies.

Potential successful cases of institutional transformation will be reported as best practices or case studies, providing concrete examples of how HEIs have successfully implemented initiatives in line with the transformation agenda. These cases will not only serve as inspiration but also offer practical insights that can be applied to other institutions. They will be integrated into the ongoing evaluation process to showcase the impact of the acceleration services on institutional changes.

By combining qualitative insights from focus groups with quantitative data from the survey, we can build a comprehensive assessment of the impact of acceleration services on institutional transformation.

3.4.1 Focus group

As part of our comprehensive testing and validation strategy, focus group sessions are crucial for gathering structured, in-depth feedback on various services within the same Transformation Agenda category. These sessions will create a dynamic and interactive setting where key stakeholders from Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) can share their experiences, expectations, and challenges related to institutional transformation. By fostering open discussions, focus groups will provide valuable insights into how our services help HEIs overcome transformation barriers and drive change in line with the European Research Area (ERA) agenda.

An iterative approach will be employed, with successive rounds of focus groups refining our understanding of users' progress in institutional transformation. This will enable us to assess the feasibility and significance of specific acceleration services while ensuring they remain aligned with the evolving needs of users. We will prioritize individuals who hold key institutional

roles and possess a deep understanding of the transformations needed to integrate acceleration services effectively. These participants will provide strategic insights on:

- The specific changes needed within HEIs to successfully adopt acceleration services.
- The expected benefits of these services at an institutional level.
- The systemic impact that acceleration services can generate across the university.

At the end of each focus group, we will administer a survey to assess the progress made in the transformation efforts of users. In particular, in these questionnaires, we will ask them to evaluate, for each service, using a Likert scale, its effectiveness in meeting the needs it addresses and in overcoming barriers (as outlined in deliverable D4.1) in institutional transformation. In addition, we will request their overall assessment of how much the Agora can enhance their daily activities. Surveys will be administered remotely. This approach allows a level of anonymity that may encourage greater honesty and candidness in their responses. Participants may feel more comfortable providing constructive criticism or sharing negative experiences without fear of judgement or bias, thereby fostering a more open and honest feedback process.

3.4.1.1 General methodology for focus group

In contrast to interviews, which provide individual-level insights by allowing participants to share personal experiences and detailed feedback in a one-on-one setting, focus groups introduce group dynamics, where participants react to one another's ideas, build on different viewpoints, and bring new insights to the surface. By conducting interviews first, we can identify core themes and initial hypotheses about user needs or barriers, and then use focus groups to validate or challenge these findings by examining how a group of users prioritizes and discusses them. The group dynamic often reveals collective insights, such as consensus, disagreements, and unexpected synergies, which highlight broader patterns and social influences on user behaviour. Combining interviews and focus groups offers a multi-layered understanding of user experiences, where interviews establish a baseline of individual needs and concerns, while focus groups expand upon these initial insights through collective discussion.

Focus groups can also be conducted at different stages of a research project to collect preliminary information on topics not yet studied, or as a means to involve the public in the research, or as a form of validation for the results obtained at the end of a project.

Focus group discussion is a technique where a researcher assembles a group of individuals to discuss a specific topic, aiming to draw from the complex personal experiences, beliefs, perceptions and attitudes of the participants through a moderated interaction.

aUPaEU members will adopt the role of a “facilitator” or a “moderator.” In this setting, the researcher facilitates or moderates a group discussion between participants and not between the researcher and the participants. Hence, the focus group participants will collectively

discuss, as a group, the topic at hand. The moderator will present the topic and guide the discussion, aiming at the involvement of all participants. Before the discussion, a list of questions (schedule or script) will be prepared as guidance for each focus group discussion session and all necessary ethical clearance will be obtained (including informed consent by all participants). After that, as the approach relies heavily on group dynamics and the synergistic interactions among participants to obtain data, participant sampling may be the most critical stage. The composition of each focus group will depend on the target users of the services to be analysed and will be carefully designed to foster open and dynamic discussions. The sampling strategy will consider the roles and experiences of individuals interacting with the services, including faculty, staff and students.

Another important consideration is the number of respondents to be invited for discussion. Although it is generally accepted that between six and eight participants are sufficient (Krueger & Casey, 2000), some studies have reported as few as four and as many as fifteen participants (e.g. Fern, 1982; Mendes de Almeida, 1980). Indeed, it is desirable to have enough people to generate diverse ideas but not so many participants that they do not have a chance to share.

A potential limitation in conducting focus group discussions is the inherent uncertainty that all those recruited will attend the discussion. Recognizing this challenge, we anticipate addressing it by organising online focus groups with fewer participants (eight individuals). The number of participants will be expanded if we achieve to conduct some discussions in person since guiding and engaging them more actively will be easier. Willingness to fully engage in a group discussion is instrumental in generating useful data and can be achieved more readily within a homogenous group (Krueger, 1994). Consequently, we plan to select participants with similar backgrounds for each discussion.

Given the small number of participants in a focus group discussion and the general design as a one-off encounter, one cannot exhaustively discuss a topic just by conducting a single group discussion. Consequently, some authors have recommended a minimum of three to four group meetings for simple research topics (Burrows & Kendall, 1997). Following the principle of theoretical saturation, we plan to run focus group discussions until a clear pattern emerges and subsequent groups produce no new information (Krueger, 1994).

One notable challenge we anticipate is the language diversity among participants from various nations. While conducting discussions in English with university stakeholders should pose no issue, there is a risk of overlooking nuanced insights. In line with Krueger and Casey's recommendation (2000), we will consider training a member of the aUPaEU to be proficient in the language rather than relying on an interpreter for moderation. Following the conclusion of each group session, the results will be translated into the analyst's language for thorough analysis. This approach aims to ensure a more nuanced understanding of participant input while maintaining the integrity of the information gathered during the discussions.

Conducting focus group discussions necessitates a collaborative effort involving a skilled facilitator and an assistant (Burrows & Kendall, 1997; Krueger, 1994). The facilitator plays a pivotal role in steering the discussion, overseeing established relationships and establishing an atmosphere of ease and comfort for participants who may be unfamiliar with one another. Likewise, the assistant's responsibilities encompass observing non-verbal cues, gauging the dynamics of the group, and meticulously documenting the overarching content of the discussion. As suggested by Kitzinger (1995), this dual team approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the data, with the assistant's contributions serving as valuable supplements to the overall findings. Data collection will incorporate both audio recording and note-taking methods. This approach, aligned with the recommendations of Stewart and Shamdasani (2015), aims to capture the richness of participants' responses while ensuring accuracy during later analysis. Regarding the duration of a focus group discussion, we consider that it should not be longer than 90-120 minutes in order not to lose the participants' interest.

3.4.1.2 Our plan

Five distinct types of focus group discussions have been identified in the literature, with two emerging types driven by the growing diversity of internet platforms (Nyumba et al., 2018). For our research, we will use a combination of traditional in-person and online focus groups to maximize the scope and reach of our discussions. Online focus groups, in particular, offer the advantage of engaging a larger and more diverse pool of participants, enabling us to gather insights from a broader audience across European universities. This will allow us to better understand the practices and needs of our users.

Each focus group will consist of average eight participants and will focus on a specific subgroup of services. Most focus group sessions will be held online to ensure we can reach a wider audience, though in-person sessions will be incorporated in the final phase of the project. Sessions will be kept to a duration of 90-120 minutes to maintain participant engagement.

All focus group sessions will be recorded, allowing for transcription of the discussions. If the sessions are conducted in languages other than English, the transcripts will be translated to facilitate analysis. The analysis of these transcripts will follow a three-step process: coding, categorizing, and interpreting. Coding involves assigning labels to segments of text that represent meaningful units of information. Categorizing entails organizing these codes into broader themes or categories that capture the main ideas or patterns in the data. Interpreting focuses on explaining and contextualizing the themes and linking them back to the research objectives.

Upon completion of the analysis, we will consolidate the findings into a comprehensive report for dissemination. This report will include participant demographics (e.g., gender, age, nationality, education level, and university role) and key quotes to highlight significant points

raised during the discussions. The report will be presented in a narrative or pointwise format, ensuring clarity and accessibility of the findings.

3.4.1.3 Focus group Protocol Steps

The objective of the Focus groups regarding institutional transformation, is to understand if and how the services are contributing to institutional transformation.

Depending on the service to be evaluated and the relevant area of the transformation agenda, we will involve people who are:

- Administrators and managers responsible for infrastructure and resource sharing (e.g., research facility managers, IT directors).
- HR representatives and academic leaders overseeing researchers career development.
- University-industry liaison officers and technology transfer managers facilitating collaboration with external R&I actors.
- Open Science coordinators and digital transformation leaders promoting knowledge sharing and open access.
- Community engagement officers and diversity/equality coordinators working on societal outreach and gender equality.

Each session will focus on a specific area of the Transformation Agenda.

Below are the key steps in planning and executing these focus group sessions:

1. Define Objectives and Scope

- Determine which services will be discussed during the session and their relevance to the specific area of the Transformation Agenda.
- Establish clear goals for each session: Have the participating universities already adopted or integrated these services? If yes, the session will focus on assessing the impact of the services and the results achieved. If not, the discussion will explore the anticipated outcomes and expected institutional changes derived from the adoption of the services.

2. Participant Selection

- Prioritize individuals holding key institutional roles with an in-depth understanding of the transformation area under discussion.
- Recruit a balanced group of 6–10 participants to ensure diverse perspectives.

3. Logistics and Scheduling

- Choose the format (online or in-person) and set a suitable date and time. Most sessions will be held remotely to accommodate participants' schedules and locations.
- Prepare any necessary materials, such as platform demonstrations or handouts, to facilitate discussion.

4. **Facilitation and Moderation**

- Appoint a moderator to guide discussions, encourage participation, and keep the session focused.
- Consider inviting external experts to provide insights on institutional transformation.
- Develop a discussion guide tailored to the session's objectives, which may vary depending on the services' adoption among the universities invited.

5. **Data Collection and Analysis**

- Obtain consent to record the session for accurate transcription.
- Transcribe, code, and analyse qualitative data to identify recurring themes and actionable insights.

Each focus group session will begin with an introduction to the selected Transformation Agenda area, followed by a discussion where participants will identify the main challenges HEIs are facing in that domain.

Next, we will present the Agora platform and the services that we believe are relevant to addressing these challenges. Participants will be invited to share their perspectives on whether these services can effectively help institutions overcome the identified barriers and what potential benefits they foresee.

The discussion will then shift to exploring the structural and procedural changes required to integrate these services within HEIs.

3.4.2 Survey

The insights from the focus groups will be instrumental in designing the survey section dedicated to the impact of acceleration services on institutional transformation. By identifying key transformation areas and relevant challenges, we can develop survey questions that quantify the perceived contribution of these services.

The survey will include:

- Likert-scale questions asking respondents to rate the extent to which our services have contributed to specific institutional changes.
- Multiple-choice questions to identify the primary challenges in adopting acceleration services.
- Open-ended questions allowing respondents to elaborate on key transformations experienced within their institutions.

3.5 Feedback Loop

Throughout testing activities, once the data are analysed, we will compile the analysed results into documentation, which will include test reports, defect logs and test metrics, to provide feedback of testing activities to the other WPs. These reports will be delivered after the associated results are analysed. We will communicate the feedback through internal meetings, shared documents, and periodic reports to ensure that all WPs stay informed and aligned. This iterative mechanism will occur continuously throughout the project duration. Indeed, one of the key advantages of cycle testing is its ability to establish a continuous feedback loop between testing activities and the development process. This ongoing process of testing, analysing data, and generating reports will establish a feedback loop between WP6 and the other WPs within the project. By conducting iterative testing of the same service, we can track its evolution over time and assess the impact of any modifications or enhancements. This process allows us to identify both strengths and areas for improvement, guiding our efforts toward validating the services listed in the catalogue, optimising the platform, and enhancing the overall user experience.

This feedback loop will aid the other WPs in the following ways:

WP2: interviews will validate the services of the acceleration services catalogue and identify emerging needs related to the services presented, providing useful information for WP2 for enhancing the service concepts. Feedback for WP2 will be delivered through meetings, where we will discuss the key findings and insights to help WP2 refine the service concepts and align them more closely with user needs. The impact of this feedback will be evident in the development of the services catalogue, first reflected in D2.2 – *“First step of the analysis, and first part of the acceleration services catalogue”* and ultimately in the final version of the catalogue in D2.3 – *“Final deliverable with a global analysis, and an aUPaEU catalogue of acceleration services”*.

WP4: feedback from interviews will favour WP4 in better defining the acceleration services business processes and describing the services from the user perspective. Meanwhile, focus group insights on institutional transformation will enrich WP4’s efforts to share good practices and streamline the operation of the acceleration services catalogue. Collectively, the outcomes of these testing activities will provide valuable input to the deliverable D4.2 *“Report on research to business policy and roadmap approach, with selected tools, methodologies and*

processes, foundations for a joint open science and innovation governance models and policies and the strategy for the involvement of societal organisations”.

WP5: the continuous feedback received from focus groups and usability tests will be an invaluable input to WP5, which is tasked with implementing and refining the MVS of the Agora of acceleration services and scaling it up to the VS. Feedback for WP5 will be delivered through periodic reports (For example, see Appendix 8.4), providing regular updates on the performance, usability, and user experience of the platform and individual services. Additionally, feedback will be discussed in meetings to enable WP5 to make informed decisions and adjustments to the MVS and ensure that the platform evolves to meet the project objectives. The impact of this feedback will be reflected in the deliverables that WP5 produces, specifically in D5.2 – *“Report on the Minimum Viable Solutions (MVS) co-built and tested by user groups”* and especially in the final deliverable D5.3 – *“Report on the deployed Viable Solution (VS) of the Agora of acceleration services”*. These deliverables will demonstrate how the feedback was integrated, leading to the scaling of the MVS into the fully deployed and validated VS.

WP7: Since WP7 focuses on communication and dissemination, the main results or successful stories from the testing activities will be shared with them through meetings. In addition, we will collaborate with WP7 to prepare the dissemination materials, ensuring that the results and success stories are effectively communicated and reach the appropriate audience.

4 Operative Plan

In the previous chapters, we focused on the testing process of individual acceleration services, outlining the specific actions and activities that would be undertaken to assess the viability and effectiveness of each service.

Now, in this section, we shift our focus to the broader testing plan, which adopts a structured, multi-cycle approach to testing the platform as a whole. Unlike the previous section, which dealt with testing the effectiveness of individual services, this section will describe how the overall testing process will unfold across three distinct testing cycles. These cycles will target different user groups—core and extended stakeholders—and will involve a variety of users with different roles, ensuring that all aspects of the platform and its services are rigorously evaluated.

By defining our operational strategy, we aim to provide a clear and actionable roadmap for the successful execution of testing activities. Through careful planning and implementation, we aim to achieve our testing objectives, generate valuable insights, and support informed decision-making that drives the overall success of the project. This plan serves as a refined version of the "*Draft Operative Plan*" outlined in D6.1.

One of the key benefits of this cycle-based approach is its ability to establish a continuous feedback loop. By testing the same services across multiple cycles, we can track their progression, evaluate any modifications or improvements, and identify areas that need further attention. This iterative process allows us to optimize the platform and its services, enhancing the overall user experience. Moreover, the continuous feedback generated throughout the testing phases will provide invaluable input to WP5, which is responsible for implementing and refining the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) and scaling it up to the Viable Solution (VS). Regular updates on the performance and usability of the platform and individual services will enable WP5 to make informed decisions, ensuring the project achieves its objectives. Furthermore, this iterative process will allow us to monitor how aUPaEU contributes to overcoming barriers to institutional transformation in the areas covered by our services.

This chapter is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of our testing plan, covering key aspects such as:

- **Testing cycles characteristics:** This section provides an overview of the activities that comprise each testing cycle.
- **Timeline:** In this section, we outline the proposed timeline for the testing phase, detailing the start and end dates for each cycle. This initial timeline serves as a framework for tracking progress, though it may be adjusted as the planning and logistical details evolve. Key checkpoints within the testing phase are also highlighted.
- **Plan for the current services:** Here, we specify the services from the acceleration services catalogue that will be tested in the first cycle. These services will be evaluated

based on predefined criteria, ensuring that we gather meaningful insights for future improvements.

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** This section outlines our strategies for engaging key stakeholders throughout the testing phase. We emphasize the importance of their active participation and collaboration to ensure the services meet the needs of all relevant parties.
- **Metrics overview:** In this section, we provide an overview of the key metrics we will use to track participation and engagement throughout the testing process. Additionally, we anticipate the KPIs we will employ to measure the success of our services, helping us gauge their effectiveness and impact.

4.1 Testing cycle characteristics

Each testing cycle is designed to assess the services in a structured and iterative manner. To streamline the process, the available services will be divided into three sets for interview-based activities. This approach ensures that each service undergoes thorough evaluation while allowing for feedback integration and continuous refinement.

For each set, the following steps will be performed sequentially:

1. **Interviews with co-creators (Initial Validation of Problem-Solution Fit).**
2. **Evaluation of the results** – providing feedback to other WPs.
3. **Interviews with potential users (Market Validation).**
4. **Evaluation of the results** – providing feedback to other WPs.
5. **Interviews with current users (Market Validation).**
6. **Evaluation of the results** – providing feedback to other WPs.

These tasks are explained in the methodology section (Chapter 3), along with the number of users involved and the goals of each activity. As the aUPaEU's methodology is an iterative process, each service will be tested multiple times, allowing us to monitor how the service improves over time.

Since the services are still under development and subject to ongoing modifications, usability testing will be conducted once they reach a more stable state. When the platform is sufficiently consolidated, usability testing will be carried out on the services available at that time.

At the end of each cycle, focus groups will be organized to assess institutional transformation. These sessions will be structured around services related to the same area of the ERA agenda, with a survey distributed at the end to gather additional insights.

Throughout the testing cycle, analysis of results will begin immediately after the interviews and continue through subsequent testing phases. The evaluation of user progress in institutional transformation will take place upon receiving the dedicated surveys. By

conducting multiple cycles, we aim to assess whether user progress evaluation improves with the development and refinement of the Agora platform and its services.

The analysis of testing results will be documented and shared with other WPs. This documentation will include test reports, defect logs, and test metrics, providing a comprehensive overview of each testing cycle.

Following the Design Thinking approach, testing results will not only validate existing solutions but also generate new ideas, uncover user needs, and inform further iterations of the project.

4.2 Timeline

We have developed a testing schedule outlined in a chart (See Figure 4.1). However, the timeline may change as it will have to adapt to the progress of implementing services on the Agora. As anticipated, our testing plan is divided into three testing cycles, each targeting three sets of services of the acceleration service catalogue.

The first testing cycle will address the initial core stakeholders of the project: aUPaEU's partner universities, Unite! Alliance and EPiCUR Alliance. The results of this cycle will serve not only to evaluate the services but also to receive feedback on the testing process. This will enable us to conduct tests more effectively in the upcoming cycles involving other universities. In the systematic arrangement of testing activities, priority is given to the Unite! Alliance over the EPiCUR Alliance, since we have already begun collaborating with the first in the ideation of the services and the Unite! Agora. Therefore, some services of the catalogue already address some of the needs expressed by Unite! Universities. Moreover, they are already current users of the platform. At the same time, the EPiCUR Alliance, while considered a future user, has been integrated into the process through WP5's development of the website module (Deliverable 5.1). This cycle will gather insights from users of both alliances to refine service development and ensure that the methodologies applied in subsequent cycles are well-structured and effective.

In the second testing cycle, the scope is extended to include additional stakeholders, particularly individuals from the new Alliances for which we are developing an Agora (the so-called "Allies"). The primary objective of this phase is to test the services that will be duplicated and integrated into these new Agoras, ensuring their adaptability and usability across different contexts. By engaging with these new Agora beneficiaries, we will gain insight into how the platform's services function beyond the initial core stakeholders. This will help identify potential scalability challenges and refine the implementation strategies for service expansion.

The third testing cycle focuses on re-engaging previous users who have already participated in earlier tests. These users will help validate whether the services—now improved or at a more advanced stage of development—meet their expectations and address their evolving needs. Additionally, this cycle will include new participants from universities involved in the first two cycles. This will allow us to gather fresh perspectives on the updated services, ensuring that they remain relevant and effective across different user groups. Depending on whether new services are developed with them as a primary target, other groups of extended stakeholders—particularly those that are not institutions or universities, such as citizens, public administrations, or industry representatives—may also be involved in selected testing activities during this cycle. Overall, this phase plays a crucial role in the iterative improvement process, helping us refine services based on continuous user feedback and ensuring that they align with the needs of various Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Alliances.

These structured cycles ensure a progressive, iterative approach to testing, enabling us to refine services and enhance their adoption across multiple university alliances.

The testing cycle time plan is as follows (see Figure 4.1):

- **Cycle 1: Testing with Unite! and EPiCUR Universities, M16-M42**
- **Cycle 2: Testing with new Agora beneficiaries, M28-M51**
- **Cycle 3: Testing with returning and new users, M37-M58**

Figure 4.1: The testing cycle time plan

4.2.1 Testing Checkpoints

To ensure a structured and effective validation process, we have defined key checkpoints that mark critical stages in testing, scaling, and finalizing the acceleration services. These checkpoints serve as reference points for assessing progress, refining the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS), and ultimately deploying the Validated Solution (VS). The main checkpoints are as follows:

Initial Testing of the First MVS Prototype: To be completed by M41 (30/05/2026) to ensure that our feedback contributes to the improvement of the MVS and supports the deliverable D5.2, "Report on the Minimum Viable Solutions (MVS) co-built and tested by user groups."

Scaling the MVS to the VS: Additional contributions to the scaling process. Checkpoint set in **M49** – 31/01/2027.

Final Testing of the Deployed VS: To be conducted by M57 (30/09/2027) to facilitate the seamless drafting of the final deliverables D6.3 "Report about the testing of the Viable Solution (VS) of the agora of acceleration services with user groups, its evaluation of the received feedback and the assessment of the progress in the institutional transformation areas" and D5.3" Report on the deployed Viable Solution (VS) of the agora of acceleration services" . Additionally, this will support the dissemination of the project's final results.

Final Event for Presentation of Validation Results: A concluding event to showcase the outcomes of the acceleration services validation. Milestone **ML6 (M60)** – 30/12/2027

Moreover, more checkpoints have been set to track individual testing activities across all cycles, providing insight into the progress of specific validation methods.

Each key activity conducted during the testing cycles will be monitored through separate checkpoints to ensure comprehensive validation and evaluation. The checkpoints for each activity are as follows:

- **Interviews (Initial Validation of Problem-Solution Fit):** Checkpoint (**M36**) – 31/12/2025. By this stage, all available services should be assessed with co-creators to validate the problem-solution fit.
- **Heuristic Evaluation on the MVS:** Checkpoint (**M40**) – 30/04/2026. At this point, heuristic evaluations should be completed for all services requiring this assessment.
- **Interviews (Market Validation):** Checkpoint (**M42**) – 30/06/2027. By this stage, all market validation interviews should be finalized.
- **Usability Testing on the VS:** Checkpoint (**M57**) – 30/09/2027. Usability testing should be conducted by this stage to allow WP5 sufficient time to implement improvements based on platform usability feedback
- **Focus Groups (Assessment of Institutional Transformation):** Checkpoint (**M57**) – 30/09/2027. The assessment of institutional transformation has a more flexible

timeline, as it is crucial to evaluate whether the platform and its services are generating a positive impact and to assess their potential future influence.

- **Survey Delivery (Customer Satisfaction + Institutional Transformation Assessment):** Checkpoint (**M59**) – 30/11/2027.

4.3 Plan for the current services

As previously outlined, the testing process is structured around three testing cycles.

The first testing cycle, which began in Month 16, focuses on evaluating the services developed during the project's initial year. As shown in Table 4.1, the available services have been categorized into three sets: Set 1, Set 2, and Set 3. The sequence of interview activities follows this categorization, ensuring a structured and systematic approach to testing.

As we move forward with the ideation of new services for the Unite! Agora, we plan to incorporate these into the final stage of the first testing cycle. Below is a table providing an overview of the services to be tested, organized by service sets. Please note that the table is illustrative rather than exhaustive. While we propose a testing order, the actual sequence may vary depending on each service's development progress. As a work package, we are highly dependent on the development plans of those conceptualizing and building the services; therefore, a service that is more mature may be tested sooner than originally scheduled.

Table 4.1 Acceleration services catalogue testing and their corresponding allocation to Testing sets

N Set	Acceleration Services	Examples
Transversal	Supply of Agoras	Unite! Agora
		EPiCUR Agora
		aUPaEU Agora
1	Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and TTOs	Epicur Research Infrastructures
		Unite! Research Infrastructures
1	Coaching and support Mechanism	Unite! Research and Innovation Proposal
2	Events, Conferences, and Workshops	Unite! Events
2	Showcases	Unite! Faculty and Staff Trainings Catalogue
		Unite! Language Tandem
		Unite! Internships Showcase
3	Accessing Grants and Funding	Unite! European Funding Opportunities Catalogue
3	Stakeholders' management	Unite! CRM platform
		aUPaEU CRM platform

This table primarily pertains to interview-based activities—namely, the initial validation of problem-solution fit and market validation. Usability testing, on the other hand, will be conducted once the services reach a more stable state. When the platform is sufficiently consolidated, usability testing will be carried out on the available services at that time.

The "Supply of Agoras" is a transversal service, as the Agora platform serves as the main service that houses all other services. Therefore, we anticipate testing the Agora platform in conjunction with the various sets of services, ensuring a holistic evaluation of how the platform integrates and supports these services.

During the second testing cycle, we will include the services that are currently under the ideation stage with the new Alliances for which we are developing a new Agora.

A new service currently under development is the Unite! TTO Catalogue. After conducting initial validation interviews, this service will be discussed in a focus group alongside the Catalogue of Research Infrastructures. Since both services fall within the same category, testing them together will help assess their complementarity and identify any unique features they may offer. Another service in the ideation phase is related to Gender Equality. Depending on its development status and pace, this new service, along with other new additions to the catalogue, will either be tested at the end of Cycle One as a new set of services or as the first set of services in Cycle Three, with final validation testing taking place at the end of Cycle Three.

4.4 Stakeholders Engagement

Design Thinking revolves around prioritising the user's needs. By collecting direct user feedback, we can make well-informed design choices, ultimately enhancing long-term user satisfaction. For us, testing is not simply about initiating service usage; it is an essential phase for gathering the insights needed to iterate and refine our services continuously. The core objective of the project is to develop a tailored Agora platform for alliances, and eventually for individual universities and research institutions not affiliated with any Alliance. Each Alliance may have distinct needs, and as such, requires different services. Given the project's strong collaboration with users to identify their needs and implement the platform's services, involving them in testing is a natural next step. Users will be motivated to participate in the testing and validation of the proposed solutions, as it will directly benefit them. Therefore, we will conduct testing activities with real users from each Agora.

For example, customizing the Agora platform for the Unite! Alliance and EPICUR Alliance to address their specific needs will naturally involve users from these alliances in the testing phase. Additionally, we will engage universities from Sister Projects in the testing process, leveraging the synergies we share with these projects and implementing some of the services specifically designed for them.

The communication and dissemination strategy of the project (outlined in D7.1) includes a variety of activities designed to engage stakeholders. These activities will not only attract new stakeholders but also provide training for both current and potential users of the services. During the “Coaching Events,” we will engage users as testers for our services, emphasizing the value they will provide by participating in the testing process, which will help us offer better services.

WP6 will define the specific programming requirements, identify the subcategories of users needed for particular testing activities, and specify which services require testing. As a result, training activities will be tailored to align with these specific services. In addition, WP4 will support coordination efforts by contributing resources, tools, and training materials that will be integrated into the acceleration services catalogue.

To further engage users, we will offer in-kind contributions to universities not affiliated with the project. The plan is to create a user group through in-kind contributions from 8 participants. These individuals will participate in three focus group sessions, each focused on different categories of acceleration services.

In addition to our planned efforts, we will actively seek out opportunities to participate in events where we can connect with potential users who may benefit from our services. For instance, we recently participated in the International Career Fair organized by Grenoble INP-UGA, where we introduced our services to students approaching graduation, many of whom expressed a potential interest in pursuing academic careers. This interaction provided valuable feedback that will guide the future development and refinement of our services. We also plan to attend other career fairs and events focused on researcher mobility, which present excellent opportunities to engage with individuals who could benefit from the services offered by the Agora platform. These include the catalogue of research infrastructure and tools designed to foster collaboration among researchers. Such events offer an ideal environment for networking, exchanging ideas, and gathering feedback, which will be essential in tailoring and improving our acceleration services to better meet the needs of our users.

4.5 Metrics overview

This section outlines key metrics related to the number of activities and engagement levels in our testing process. Our goal is to involve participants from at least four Alliances and 20 universities during the testing phase. For each acceleration service example, we have defined the minimum number of distinct testing sessions required, as detailed in Table 4.2

Table 4.2: metrics overview for each service

Activity for each service	Metrics
Interviews with co-creators	At least 1 interview for each service
Interviews with potential	At least 5 interviews for each service in each cycle the service is tested
Interviews with current users	At least 5 interviews for each service in each cycle the service is tested
Focus Groups	At least 2 sessions for each service
Heuristic Evaluation	3 evaluations for at least 2 services
Usability testing	1-3 sessions in each cycle

For clarification, we plan to conduct at least five interviews per service in each cycle, engaging both potential users and current users. In cases where a service addresses multiple distinct target groups, we will opt to conduct five interviews per target group. A relevant example of this approach is the Catalogue of Research Infrastructures service, which serves two primary user groups: those managing research infrastructure seeking visibility and new collaboration opportunities on the platform, and researchers who use the platform to search for available research infrastructure.

In addition, as our platform offers a collection of services, usability testing should strike a balance between testing the overall platform and individual services. Here's a more refined approach to consider:

- **Overall Platform Usability:** It's important to test the usability of the platform as a whole to ensure that users can navigate through various services, access information efficiently, and move between different features without confusion. This helps identify potential navigation issues, overall user experience challenges, or areas of improvement in the platform's design and functionality.
- **Single Service Usability:** For specific services, like the catalogue of research infrastructure, usability testing should focus on how effectively users can perform tasks within that service (e.g., search for infrastructure, contact providers). This is important because, while the platform may work well overall, the user experience for specific services may still present unique challenges that need attention.

We will combine the usability sessions of related services within one session to capture insights on both the overall platform and specific services, especially for those services that are easy to use and integrate into the broader user experience.

4.5.1 KPIs

We will design KPIs to track the success of our services, ensuring they effectively address user needs and contribute to institutional transformation. These KPIs will cover various aspects,

including usability, user engagement, service effectiveness, and overall impact. Below are some general KPIs that can be applied across all the services offered.

General KPIs for evaluating acceleration services:

1. Usability and Accessibility

- Percentage of users who find the service intuitive
- Average time required to complete a key task on the service.
- Number of technical support requests per service.
- Number of high-severity design issue.
- Number of low-severity design issues.

2. User satisfaction and Engagement

- Average satisfaction score on a Likert scale (e.g., 1-5).
- Percentage of users who use the service regularly.
- Average session duration on the platform.
- Likelihood of users recommending the service to others.

3. Effectiveness and Relevance of the Service

- Percentage of users who find the service helpful for their work/study.
- Number of suggestions collected for future improvements.
- Number of new features requested and implemented.

4. Impact on work

- Percentage of users who report improved efficiency due to the service.
- Number of internal processes optimized through service adoption.
- Number of collaborations or projects initiated via the service.

Below are sample KPIs for the "Catalogue of Research Infrastructures" service, which can serve as a template for developing new KPIs for other services.

A. Diversity of research fields and specializations on the platform

These KPIs evaluate the breadth and depth of research infrastructures available on the platform across various research fields, as well as how this diversity contributes to collaboration and innovation.

- **Total Number of Research Fields Supported on the Platform:** Track the total number of distinct research fields or domains represented by the research infrastructures listed on the platform.
- **Number of Interdisciplinary Collaborations Across Fields:** track the number of collaborations that bridge multiple research fields. This can help assess the service's role in fostering interdisciplinary research.

B. Impact of the services on Accelerating the Institutional Transformation

These KPIs assess how the Catalogue of Research Infrastructure can contribute to the Institutional transformation of HEIs.

- **Institutional Adoption Rate:** Percentage of universities and research institutions adopting the platform's infrastructure services, reflecting institutional transformation toward digital collaboration and resource sharing.
- **External Partnership Formation:** Number of partnerships with industry, government, or other stakeholders formed through the platform, signalling institutional expansion into external collaborative networks.

The KPIs above will be supplemented with additional insights and metrics derived from user interviews and focus groups, which will help us gather more qualitative feedback and refine the service offerings. These additional KPIs will focus on specific needs, barriers, and suggestions for improvement.

1. User Perceived Value:

- How well do users perceive the service as meeting their needs?
- Do users see the service as improving collaboration opportunities and innovation?

2. Service Fit with User Needs:

- Percentage of users who believe the service fits well with their current work/study requirements.
- User feedback on unmet needs or gaps in the service that could be addressed in future iterations.

3. Barriers to Adoption and Engagement:

- Common challenges faced by users in adopting or engaging with the service.
- Frequency of specific technical or operational issues raised by users during interviews/focus groups.

4. Impact on Collaboration and Networking:

- User perceptions of how the service can foster new collaborations or networks beyond their institution.
- Feedback on the service's role in facilitating interdisciplinary or inter-institutional collaboration.

By collecting and analysing both quantitative and qualitative data from these KPIs, we will continuously improve our services and ensure they remain aligned with the evolving needs of users and institutions.

5 Preliminary results

We have initiated the testing phase by selecting an initial set of services for evaluation. As outlined in the table from the previous chapter, this first set includes the Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and Research and Innovation Proposal.

To begin the assessment, we conducted interviews with co-creators and started gathering insights from potential users. A total of 30 interviews have been completed, with additional sessions planned for March and April. We have completed the interviews with co-creators regarding the first two sets of services (as indicated in Table 4.2). In April, we will finalize we will finalize the interviews with potential users for the first set of services, while also initiating interviews for the second set.

Heuristic evaluation has also begun, with the first report expected to be submitted to WP5 in April.

Additionally, during our participation in the Grenoble Career Fair 2024, we took the opportunity to present two additional services that were not originally included in the initial testing set: the Doctoral Course Catalogue and Internship Opportunities. These services were introduced because of their strong relevance to late-stage students. Given their alignment with the needs of this audience, we considered them valuable for gathering early feedback. Both services fall under the broader Showcases category. This approach has enabled us to collect preliminary insights on a wider range of services, further refining our understanding of user needs and expectations. During the event, we had the opportunity to interview 3 students.

It is important to note that this chapter presents the preliminary results thus far. A more detailed analysis will be conducted once the interview phase for each service and testing cycle is complete, allowing us to provide greater clarity in the data. In the meantime, any usability improvement suggestions that emerged from the interviews, along with requests for additional features, have been tracked and communicated to WP5.

As an example, the First Summary Report on Testing Activities (Periodic Feedback and Improvement Report for Platform Services – Report #1), is available in Appendix 8.4. Subsequent reports will be periodically shared with WP5 to support service improvements and integrate ongoing user feedback.

5.1 Summary feedback on Catalogue of Research Infrastructures

We conducted 15 interviews regarding the “Catalogue of research infrastructures” service: 3 with co-creators and 12 with potential users. The co-creators, all research infrastructure specialists at their respective institutions, were interviewed from Aalto University, UPC, and POLITO. For potential users, we initially engaged individuals with similar profiles based on recommendations from the co-creators. These potential users work in the same field and could have an interest in the service. Specifically, we interviewed 7 administrative and technical staff from POLITO, TU Graz, U Lisboa, and INP-UGA. As we progressed, we expanded our interviews to researchers from Partner Universities who will ultimately use the service to connect with these infrastructures. This approach allows us to compare researchers' perspectives with those of university administrative staff and assess the service's market value. Among the researchers interviewed, we included both early-career researchers and senior faculty members, totaling 5 participants from POLITO and INP-UGA.

Indeed, since the end users of the service are researchers looking for infrastructures to collaborate with, it is crucial to collect their insights interviewing them. This service has two main user groups: service providers (research infrastructure staff) and end users (researchers). Additionally, it has the potential to support the work of university administrative staff. For these reasons, we expanded our target audience to explore how different user groups have distinct needs and perceive the service's value differently. We also had the opportunity to hear the opinions of 3 master's students nearing graduation.

During the interviews, it was acknowledged that the Agora platform holds significant potential in addressing critical gaps in the visibility and accessibility of research infrastructures, both within universities and beyond. Key findings emphasize the platform's value in streamlining access to resources, fostering collaboration, and supporting the mobility of early-career researchers.

Furthermore, the platform's ability to connect diverse infrastructures and simplify the user journey through managed contacts has been widely recognized as one of its unique strengths. However, feedback also highlights the importance of addressing existing challenges and implementing further enhancements to maximize the platform's overall impact.

The following section provides detailed feedback from the interviews conducted.

5.1.2 Value of the service

5.1.2.1 Addressing the need for a structured and accessible research infrastructure catalogue

The majority of co-creators highlighted that the initial demand for such a service emerged primarily from research infrastructure managers and university staff. These stakeholders sought more effective ways to organize and promote their institutions' research offerings. Many universities reported facing similar challenges, underscoring the necessity of structured visibility:

"At our university, the inspiration for developing this service stemmed from the need to better organize and promote our extensive resources and capabilities, both internally and externally."

"Despite our reputation as a strong technical university, many stakeholders—particularly in industry—were unaware of the full extent of our laboratories and research infrastructures. This lack of awareness sometimes led to surprising discoveries about our capabilities."

"The industry recognized our technical excellence but often had no visibility into our portfolio of research infrastructures. We felt an urgent need to better organize and showcase these resources."

Some universities have already included their research infrastructures in external catalogs. For example, Aalto University lists its infrastructures in the Nordic Five Tech (N5T) Alliance catalog. However, these existing resources are often limited to simple listings and do not provide direct interaction between researchers and infrastructure managers. As one respondent pointed out:

"Ideally, I would like to have a catalogue at a European level. Agora's model could serve as a blueprint for a broader European catalogue."

5.1.2.2 Perceived value of the catalogue of research infrastructure

Both co-creators and potential users have recognized the significant value of the Catalogue of Research Infrastructures service. The platform effectively addresses key needs related to visibility, accessibility, and collaboration within the research ecosystem.

The key benefits identified in the interviews are:

- **Unified Infrastructure Access** – The service consolidates diverse research capabilities across multiple universities, facilitating global outreach and more efficient resource utilization.
- **Streamlined Connections** – Researchers can access multiple infrastructures without the need to individually contact each institution, reducing administrative burdens.

- **Comprehensive Offerings** – By networking various institutions, the platform enables universities to complement each other’s capabilities, supporting more complex and multidisciplinary research projects.
- **Enhanced Collaboration** – The service fosters cross-institutional and interdisciplinary collaboration, driving innovation and efficiency in research activities.
- **Beyond a Simple Directory** – Unlike static catalogues, the platform provides an active connection process. A service manager filters contact requests, ensuring that infrastructure managers receive relevant inquiries rather than being overwhelmed with unsuitable requests.
- **Increased Utilization of Research Infrastructures** – By making infrastructures more visible and accessible, the service helps maximize their usage rates. As one interviewee noted: *“Our user rate is below the optimal level for our research infrastructure.”*
- **Greater Visibility for University Resources** – The service offers a clear and accessible method to showcase available resources, increasing awareness both internally and externally.

Although the service was originally designed to meet the needs of suppliers (universities and infrastructure providers), it has proven to deliver significant value for end users—researchers seeking access to infrastructures. Specifically, researchers have highlighted how the service improves access to research infrastructures. A unified catalogue offers an efficient way to connect users with the right resources. As one interviewee shared, *“Having everything in a catalogue is incredibly beneficial. Instead of searching on Google and potentially encountering outdated contacts, a catalogue where each infrastructure includes a contact function gives me confidence that I’ll receive a response. It also makes the search for the right infrastructure much more immediate and allows me to easily identify available resources at a specific university without having to look elsewhere.”* Additionally, a senior researcher emphasized how the service can play a key role in supporting PhD students by helping them find the appropriate infrastructure for organizing their visiting activities. She noted, *“At the moment, I’ve relied heavily on word of mouth to help my PhD students identify potential infrastructures to contact for organizing their visits. I believe this tool could greatly improve the efficiency of this process. What I like is that the information is filtered, while when I search on Google, I need to assess its relevance. It feels like a curated, useful collection of information. Since the catalog is hosted on the Agora of the alliance, I trust that I will receive a response. For example, last year I contacted five different infrastructures by searching online, and only two responded. I trust that the sense of community and the expectation of a response will be stronger here, and I’m confident that this service won’t just be a showcase but will foster real collaboration.”*

Students and early-career researchers find this service particularly valuable, especially those unfamiliar with available research infrastructures and reliant on their supervisors for guidance. By simplifying the process of identifying and accessing research facilities during academic visits, the catalogue enhances mobility and fosters international collaboration. PhD students

and junior researchers benefit the most, as it provides structured access to external research infrastructures, making cross-border research opportunities more accessible and efficient.

5.1.3 Barriers to adoption

Several barriers to the adoption of the Catalogue of Research Infrastructure service emerged from the interviews. These barriers can be broadly categorized into four main types:

1. **Institutional Barriers** – Challenges related to the internal structures and administrative processes of universities, which affect the integration and promotion of the platform.
2. **Financial Barriers** – Constraints related to the costs associated with accessing research infrastructures, particularly travel expenses for early-career researchers.
3. **User Experience Barriers** – Issues concerning the usability of the service, including clarity of the contact process and user engagement with the platform.
4. **Organizational Barriers** – Uncertainty about who manages the infrastructure profiles and responds to contact requests, potentially leading to inefficiencies in communication and lost collaboration opportunities.

1. Institutional Barriers

A key challenge is the need for dedicated coordination within each university to ensure the platform's smooth integration and continued relevance. Ideally, a designated staff member within the university's research infrastructure support office should oversee the platform's development, verify the accuracy and consistency of infrastructure profiles, and update information as new infrastructures are created or meet the inclusion criteria.

One interviewee suggested:

"It would be helpful to establish a periodic working group or a meeting where all relevant contacts are updated on profile changes, potential new additions, and the platform's progress, including how well it is being received by end users."

Additionally, for researchers to engage actively with the platform, universities must invest effort into promoting and embedding the service within their workflows. As one interviewee noted:

"Ideally, each university should have a reference page for research infrastructures within its own website, with a direct link to the catalogue of shared infrastructures available on the Agora website."

While many supported this approach, some pointed out that institutional regulations could make uniform implementation across universities challenging.

2. Financial Barriers

A significant barrier to adoption is the financial burden associated with accessing research infrastructures. Travel expenses, in particular, present a major challenge for early-career researchers, as securing funding for mobility is often more difficult than arranging access to host institutions.

One interviewee emphasized this issue:

"Travel is expensive, and for a junior researcher, finding the funds to cover travel costs is the tricky part. Arranging a host institution is relatively easy, but financing the visit is much more complicated."

This highlights the need for targeted support mechanisms, such as dedicated grants, institutional funding programs, or more efficient application processes for travel funding, to facilitate researcher mobility.

3. User Experience Barriers

Some researchers have expressed concerns that the lack of clear information about who receives contact requests might discourage users from engaging with the service. The presence of a generic "contact" button, without additional details, leaves users uncertain about who will respond and whether their inquiry will reach the right person. Some may even prefer direct contact to ensure they know exactly who they are communicating with. To address this, a clearer explanation of the contact process on the service page has been suggested. The platform should specify that users send a message through the system, which is then forwarded to the responsible person managing the research infrastructure, with an email notification confirming receipt.

4. Organizational Barriers

Another critical issue concerns the management of infrastructure profiles and contact requests. It is unclear who should be responsible for reading and responding to inquiries. Additionally, there is uncertainty about who will regularly update the profiles with information regarding current activities, available opportunities, and specific requests related to the infrastructure. If the head of the infrastructure is designated for these tasks, there is a risk that they may be too busy with their primary responsibilities to consistently check, update the profiles, and respond to requests. As a result, delays or missed responses could hinder the effectiveness of the service and limit collaboration opportunities.

5.1.4 Key suggestions and Desired Features

The following suggestions for improving the service were gathered from the interviews:

1. Target Audience Expansion

- Currently, the service appears to cater primarily to researchers. To increase visibility among a wider range of stakeholders and establish new collaborations, it would be beneficial to use Agora as a platform to reach different audiences and promote the services offered by individual research infrastructures.
- Expanding access to companies would be particularly beneficial. To achieve this, the platform should clearly indicate which research infrastructures offer business services. A dedicated section or filter highlighting infrastructures available for commercial use would help businesses navigate the platform more effectively. Additionally, a tailored user journey for companies should be introduced to facilitate access to relevant resources.

2. Cost and Pricing Information

- Providing pricing details for research infrastructure services could increase transparency and help potential users make informed decisions.
- However, pricing structures often vary significantly across universities and research infrastructures, making standardization challenging. The key challenge is to establish a transparent pricing methodology that can adapt to both national and international contexts. While some interviewees advocate for including pricing information, the inconsistencies in internal pricing structures underscore the complexity of implementing a uniform approach.
- A potential approach is to explore the feasibility of displaying pricing information while ensuring flexibility in how it is presented.

3. Technical Staff and Booking Process

- Participants suggested that a search function to identify research infrastructures with available technical staff would be highly useful.
- Integrating detailed information on technical staff availability as a filter option could enhance usability and facilitate better support for users.
- Additionally, streamlining the booking process is essential. Providing clear booking instructions, including direct links to booking websites on each infrastructure's profile page, would improve accessibility and user experience.

4. Reporting and Impact Visibility

- A suggestion has been made to provide regular updates, reports, or data on the number of contacts made through the platform. This would allow universities to monitor which infrastructures are receiving contact and how often, providing insight into the platform's actual impact on visibility.

- By implementing a reporting feature, universities can gain a better understanding of which infrastructures are being most frequently accessed, enabling them to assess the effectiveness of the platform in increasing exposure and fostering collaboration. This data-driven approach could inform future improvements and help stakeholders measure the success of the platform.

5.1.5 Userface and Usability enhancements

Based on the feedback collected during the interviews, the following improvements are suggested to enhance the platform's user experience and accessibility:

1. **Consistent and Detailed Instructure Profiles**

- Research infrastructure profiles currently lack consistency. Some universities provide less detailed descriptions, which may give users the impression that their infrastructures offer fewer services.
- Suggested improvement: Standardize profile formatting to ensure completeness and clarity. Each profile should include detailed descriptions, high-quality images, relevant keywords, and direct links to the dedicated research infrastructure website.

2. **Keyword and Filter Functionality**

- The "**Filter by Keywords**" section causes some confusion due to the way the individual keywords are written and their ordering.
- Suggested improvement: Reorganize keywords for clarity, such as displaying them alphabetically and removing ambiguous symbols or unexplained pinned keywords. Simplify the filtering system by eliminating unnecessary filters that clutter the page and hinder usability.

3. **Enhancements to Profile Navigation and Search**

- The interviewees expressed a need for more detailed information on research infrastructures—not just their existence in a specific field, but also practical details on how to access them and the services they offer.
- The suggestion is to add more information to the research infrastructure profiles, including details on remote access options (and what is meant by "remote access"), online booking capabilities (when applicable), the type of support provided by technical staff, their availability, and clear indications of the conditions for external users to access resources (such as whether training is required and the type of training needed). Visually integrate these related details into a coherent layout to enhance user experience and accessibility.
- Some interviewees have also mentioned that it would be visually appealing to have the logos of the universities connected to the research infrastructures.

4. Accessibility and Information Clarity

- Potential users initially assume that research infrastructures do not have dedicated websites because the link is attached to the phrase "further information," making it less visible.
- Suggested improvement: Make the link more prominent and place it at the top of the profile page. Clearly label it as "Official Research Infrastructure Website" rather than using the ambiguous "further information."

5. Clarification of Eligibility Criteria and Inclusion of Additional Resources

- It would be useful to clearly state the criteria for being listed as a research infrastructure in the catalogue. This transparency would help users better understand the types of infrastructures that meet the platform's inclusion standards.
- Furthermore, consideration could be given to creating a similar service or a subsection for resources that do not strictly meet the criteria but are still valuable and sought after for collaboration. As one young researcher mentioned: *"I focus on entrepreneurship, and I'd love to map the centers within universities that deal with entrepreneurship. However, when I search the platform, I can't find anything on this topic. If you could add types of resources that don't meet your criteria, or at least make it clear when I go to the service, what the clear definition of 'research infrastructure' is, that would be very helpful."* This would allow users to identify and access valuable resources, even if they do not fall within the strict boundaries of the current definition of research infrastructure, thus broadening the scope of collaboration opportunities.

5.2 Summary feedback on Research and Innovation Proposals

So far, three interviews have been conducted with co-creators regarding the "Research and Innovation Proposals" service. One co-creator is from UPC University (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya), while two are from POLITO (Politecnico di Torino). These individuals are actively involved in supporting research at their respective universities and are part of the IRIS network, a joint network of Integrated Research and Innovation Services.

Their feedback underscores the service's potential to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and streamline the proposal-matching process. By enhancing dissemination efforts, improving the organization of proposal types, and refining the user interface, the tool could better serve researchers and support offices, ensuring its effectiveness as a practical and widely adopted solution.

We then began interviewing potential users, focusing on two key groups: professionals working in research support offices and researchers. So far, we have conducted six interviews with potential users from POLITO and INP-UGA.

5.2.1 Value of the service

The value of the "Research and Innovation Proposals" service, as perceived by the interviewed co-creators, lies primarily in its ability to facilitate connections between researchers from diverse backgrounds, addressing the growing need for interdisciplinarity in research proposals. As the demand for interdisciplinary collaboration continues to rise, this service provides an essential and practical platform for enhancing cooperation among Unite! researchers.

While traditional channels for connecting faculty and researchers, such as specific networks, word-of-mouth, or administrative offices, exist, they often fail to adequately support the increased need for cross-disciplinary collaboration. This service addresses that gap by offering a dedicated channel that enables faculty to connect with researchers from other universities who possess complementary expertise. As one of the interviewees highlighted:

"The tool was not designed to serve as a "virtual office" but rather as a solution to provide immediate, practical outcomes. Before its introduction, researchers typically relied on informal networks or administrative offices to identify potential collaborators. This service simplifies and accelerates the process, enabling researchers to independently identify contacts while allowing administrative offices to monitor proposal notifications and proactively identify collaboration opportunities."

The interviewed participants also believe the service could offer significant added value by supporting collaborations during Unite! events and other field-specific initiatives. One participant noted:

"In the past, such activities were managed manually, often using spreadsheets. The platform now could streamline and systematize this process, improving efficiency and facilitating the matching of researchers with shared interests, thus increasing the potential for successful collaboration."

The perceived value of the service varies among different types of researchers. Senior researchers, for example, emphasized the tool's potential value in finding partners for project proposals. Although they do not currently use tools like this, they would certainly use it once the service reaches a more mature state.

Young researchers, on the other hand, see the tool as a valuable resource for other types of collaborations beyond project proposals. They believe the platform could be particularly useful for finding partners to collaborate on writing papers. One young researcher shared their perspective:

"When I was doing my PhD, I have collaborated with another doctoral student in my department who worked on a complementary aspect of my research topic. Why don't we explore this research question together? I would love to find someone interested in pursuing a complementary study with me. But, how can I find people? By attending conferences, building network, through word-

of-mouth on LinkedIn, or asking my supervisors. A more direct platform could be really helpful, especially in connecting with researchers from other countries".

Young researchers also noted that the platform should differentiate between funding proposals and other types of collaboration to better align with the needs of early-stage researchers, such as PhD students and research fellows, who are often more interested in collaboration for writing papers rather than large project proposals.

5.2.2 Barriers to adoption

Some barriers to the adoption of the Research and Innovation Proposals service emerged from the interviews. These barriers can be summarized in:

1. **Lack of Awareness and Visibility** – Barriers related to the visibility of the service and the awareness among potential users about its benefits and existence.
2. **Integration Barriers** – Barriers related to integrating the service into existing workflows and systems within universities, including organizational and technical challenges.
3. **Communication Barriers** – Barriers related to the clarity, completeness, and personal engagement in the proposals, which affect the communication and collaboration process.

1. Lack of Awareness and Visibility

One of the main barriers to the adoption of the Research and Innovation Proposals service is the risk that its effectiveness could be limited by a lack of awareness and visibility. While the tool is designed to streamline the matching process, its success heavily depends on its visibility and active promotion across academic institutions. If researchers and support offices are unaware of the platform's benefits or if its usage is not actively promoted within their networks, the tool's potential may not be fully realized.

An important suggestion from the co-creators is to establish a notification system to disseminate published proposals more effectively. By using communication channels such as the IRIS network's mailing list and university offices responsible for research, the platform could ensure that collaboration requests reach the right audience. Without these additional communication flows, proposals might go unnoticed, limiting valuable collaboration opportunities.

2. Integration Barriers

Another significant challenge involves integrating the service into existing systems and workflows within universities. Some institutions may face technical or organizational difficulties in adopting a new platform, particularly in terms of the time and resources needed to incorporate the service into their operations.

For example, staff in university offices responsible for research would need to dedicate time to selecting and sharing the most suitable proposals with various categories of researchers. Furthermore, researchers would need to incorporate the platform into their daily routines to engage with new proposals continuously. This may require training or support to ensure researchers actively check for updates and engage with the platform's content. The lack of integration into existing workflows can hinder the adoption and frequent use of the service.

3. Communication Barriers

Feedback from researchers emphasized the importance of including personal details and background information in proposals to make the contact process more engaging. If proposals are presented in a generic way, without insight into the person behind them, it may discourage potential collaborators from reaching out.

Providing information about the proposer—whether it's a researcher or an administrator—is seen as essential for building trust and encouraging collaboration. Moreover, each proposal should clearly specify the type of collaborator being sought: Is it a university, a whole team, or an individual researcher? Without this level of detail, potential collaborators may be hesitant to initiate communication.

Additionally, the proposal should outline the desired skills or expertise of the collaborator. When the required profile is clearly defined, individuals who match that profile are more likely to engage. However, when proposals lack clarity, potential partners may feel uncertain or reluctant to offer their collaboration.

5.2.3 Desired Features

Several additional features were suggested to enhance the service:

- **Notification System:** There is a request to develop a notification system within the IRIS network, as well as for broader research support offices, to facilitate the dissemination of published proposals. Once a collaboration request is posted, it should be disseminated across additional channels to ensure visibility. Proposals should be communicated to the relevant stakeholders, such as the IRIS group mailing list or university offices dealing with research and teaching.
- **Clearer Categorization:** A clearer categorization between research proposals and other types of collaboration, such as joint papers or workshops, would be helpful. This would allow research support offices to focus specifically on research-related proposals, which align more closely with their responsibilities. Additionally, a thematic categorization could significantly improve the user experience, allowing for quick identification of proposals of interest.
- **Event Organizer Section:** A dedicated section for event organizers to easily find relevant proposals was also recommended. In past projects, workshops were

organized where researchers with shared interests were invited to collaborate on specific calls. This tool could act as a matchmaking service, helping form initial groups that can meet during events, exchange ideas, and develop potential proposals. A separate section for this purpose would improve the process's effectiveness and organization.

5.2.4 Interface and Usability Enhancements

To further improve the user experience and streamline the proposal-matching process, several interface and usability enhancements were suggested by the interviewed co-creators. These changes aim to increase the efficiency and clarity of the platform, making it more user-friendly for both researchers and administrative staff. The following enhancements were particularly highlighted:

- **Sorting Functionality:** Adding a sorting feature to allow users to organize proposals by recent activity or deadlines would be beneficial for better navigation and time management.
- **Improved Proposal Visibility:** Currently, users need to open each proposal to determine its purpose, such as whether it's for a research project, a collaboration request, or a paper co-authorship. It was suggested to add tags or labels beneath proposal titles to indicate the type of request, enhancing clarity at a glance. Additionally, using color-coded banners for each proposal title, based on its theme or type, could further enhance visibility and allow users to quickly identify the nature of the proposal.
- **Dedicated Subsection for Funding Proposals:** A dedicated subsection for funding proposals would help university research support offices quickly access the most relevant proposals. This section should be separate from other content for better focus and easier navigation.

5.3 Summary feedback on Unite! Faculty and Staff Trainings Catalogue and Unite! Language Tandem

We present the preliminary feedback on these two services together, as they were developed by the same co-creator and are both part of the "Unite! Faculty & Staff Community Platform," created by the aUPaEU team. The co-creator for this service interviewed is a project manager from Grenoble INP-UGA. As part of the interview process, we aim to gather insights from researchers and university staff working in HR departments, mobility offices, and faculty training offices. Our goal is to understand whether these services are useful to them and whether they would actively use them. Up to know, we have conducted three interviews with young researchers from POLITO on both the services.

5.3.1 Value of the service

The initial need was to find a centralized space to post training opportunities and mobility information for Unite! Staff. Given that Agora serves as an acceleration services hub, they found it to be the ideal platform. The co-creator is highly satisfied with the services evolution, emphasizing the importance of having all information on the same platform while maintaining direct control over the service to update the catalogue as needed. Sustainability emerged as key concern: services should be easy to manage and widely accessible. The solution provided by the aUPaEU team aligns well with this need – offering something manageable, hands-off, and resembling a catalogue or forum.

For the **Training Catalogue**, the main benefit is providing courses that are not duplicated at individual universities. Researchers seeking professional development or courses beyond their home university's offerings can find valuable opportunities through this service. The inclusion of mobility opportunities further enhances the platform's value.

The idea of **Language Tandem** service emerged later. Unite! already offers a similar service for students, and the goal was to extend it to staff to strengthen the Unite! community. This required features such as user profiles and contact options. The existing student tandem program is hosted on a separate platform, but staff members have different needs. Unlike students who have specific registration periods, staff participation should be more flexible. The main goal is to enhance networking among researchers.

Language Tandem does not have a specific target audience, it can be useful for both early-career and senior researchers. It is particularly relevant for those traveling, as it helps them familiarize themselves with local languages and cultures.

The co-creator believes the solutions developed by the aUPaEU team are highly effective and versatile. Any missing elements were successfully addressed in collaboration with the team. However, one key limitation is the lack of real-time statistics—currently, they must manually request data. A dashboard displaying service usage metrics would be a valuable addition.

5.3.1.1 Value perceived by potential users

Regarding the **Training Staff service**, both interviewees found it highly valuable. One interviewee was particularly excited to have found a dedicated space to publish Erasmus mobility programs from their university, emphasizing that the platform significantly enhances the visibility of mobility and training opportunities, making it easier for staff to access relevant resources. Another major advantage highlighted was the availability of open courses from different universities, as many users are currently only familiar with private training platforms.

The interviewees also noted that the platform effectively addresses their need for courses supporting teaching activities, methodology training, and resources for integrating new teaching approaches. Its integration within Unite! Agora further enhances accessibility and

familiarity, making it more convenient for users. However, some aspects require clarification, such as whether external researchers can access the courses and who the specific target audience is. Additionally, a navigation issue was identified: when users access the Unite! Faculty & Staff Community Platform, it is unclear how to return to the main Agora site. To improve usability, a notice should inform users that they are being redirected to an external URL.

As for the **Language Tandem service**, one respondent stated that they would not use it due to time constraints but acknowledged that others might find it beneficial. They acknowledged that the service is particularly valuable for mobility, as it helps users connect with local partners, better understand local customs, and receive guidance. While not considered essential, it is perceived as a "nice-to-have" feature that supports language practice, networking, and cultural exchange.

5.3.2 Barriers to adoption

The perceived barriers are mainly:

1. **Usability Barrier** – Barriers related to the visibility and clarity of how users perceive and access the services.
2. **Institutional and Organizational Barriers** – Barriers related to the involvement of university departments and institutional policies affecting the promotion and adoption of the platform.

1. Usability Barrier

The platform's design and structure currently pose challenges to user navigation and service identification. A key issue highlighted in interviews is the lack of visibility of services within the Unite! Agora platform. When users access the platform and see the two services alongside other offerings, they may not immediately recognize them as important or easily distinguishable. Additionally, the transition to a different URL and the menu structure is not intuitive, which could confuse users and hinder their ability to quickly locate these services. The absence of clear distinctions between services, coupled with the unintuitive navigation, disrupts the overall user experience.

To address this, implementing a dedicated banner within Unite! Agora specifically for the Unite! Community Platform could help clarify the transition to an external site and increase the prominence of the services. This enhancement would make it easier for users to find and engage with the services directly, improving the user's experience and increasing the likelihood of their use.

2. Institutional and Organizational Barriers

In addition to the visibility challenges, gaining users' engagement with the platform and its services requires active promotion from university offices. Universities could promote the platform internally to increase visibility and usage, but institutional policies and priorities might present challenges. For example, HR departments are typically focused on their own training catalogues and may not prioritize promoting a shared catalogue, especially if it requires additional effort or changes to established systems.

This raises the question of how best to approach internal promotion within each university. Different institutions might have varied levels of support or willingness to promote the shared catalogue, depending on their policies and organizational structure. Overcoming these challenges will require thoughtful strategies and collaboration with university departments to ensure effective dissemination and use of the platform.

5.3.3 Desired Features

The following suggestions for improving the service were gathered from the interviews:

- A notification system should be implemented to alert the communication manager when new courses are added, ensuring timely dissemination of information. This feature should be validated with HR specialists at universities to align with their needs.
- A chat function could facilitate peer-to-peer exchanges, making it easier for users to find suitable partners for training or language tandem activities. Enabling direct communication would create a more informal, friendly, and accessible environment for collaboration.
- For the Language Tandem service, could be nice to have a sort of real-time statistics—currently, data must be manually requested. A dashboard displaying service usage metrics, including the number of successful matches, would provide valuable insights into user engagement.
- Additionally, some points require clarification, such as whether external researchers can access the courses and who the specific target audience is.
- Navigation issue: when users access the Unite! Faculty & Staff Community Platform, it is unclear how to return to the main Agora site. To improve usability, a notice should inform users that they are being redirected to an external URL.

5.5 Summary feedback on Unite! Events

The Unite! Events feature was introduced as an internal decision by the team to expand the Agora platform's functionalities. Unlike other services, it was not developed in response to a specific user need but rather as a natural extension of the platform. As a result, there are no true co-creators for this service.

However, we do have a champion for Unite! Events: a marketing and communication professional from Aalto and Unite! This person used the service to organize a series of Unite! webinars held on March 12, 2025. The platform was utilized to manage student registrations, provide relevant session details, and include links to Zoom webinars.

After the event, we gathered feedback from this user. She reported:

"For my team, Unite! Events was useful. We needed a way for students to not only register but also access the session links and add them to their calendars. In the past, we had hundreds of registrations, but many students didn't show up. Having the event on their calendar helped, as it sent reminders. Overall, everything worked well—it was fantastic, though it took some time to set up. One issue was that email notifications were not sent immediately but instead at scheduled intervals. There were some timing glitches, possibly related to time zones, which caused some frustration. People contacted me about these issues. Would I use it again? Yes, I would!"

5.5.1 Suggested improvements

The following suggestions were provided during the interview:

- **Event Listings on a Single Page:** During the period I used the service, only the Unite! webinars were listed, making it easy to view all relevant events at a glance. Introducing a dedicated section for specific event series or institutional events under a single "umbrella" could improve usability and organization.
- **Event Categorization:** Introducing different sections within Unite! Events could help users filter and find relevant events more efficiently.

5.6 Preliminary results on other services

We tested additional services alongside the Catalogue of Research Infrastructures during the [International Career Fair organized by Grenoble INP-UGA](#), where aUPaEU had the opportunity to set up an Agora stand aimed at students seeking to broaden their academic horizons. As part of this initiative, we organized one roundtable with 13 students and held three informal meetings to present and discuss the Agora platform. These discussions served a dual purpose: showcasing available opportunities and gathering feedback on the first services developed by aUPaEU.

On this occasion, we brought forward the testing of two services that we had initially planned to test later: the Doctoral Course Catalogue (providing access to a diverse range of doctoral courses from Unite! universities) and Internship Opportunities (exploring potential positions within the Unite! community). These services were chosen because they as these services are more directly relevant to students.

There was strong interest in exploring internship opportunities offered by laboratories across various European countries, as well as in learning about PhD programs available within Unite!

universities. Students expressed a clear desire to gain international experience, emphasizing their ambition to travel and expand their horizons. They hope the Agora platform will become a key tool to help them step beyond their home universities, providing essential information to support bold steps, facilitate connections, and build valuable networks early in their research careers.

5.3.4 Summary feedback on Doctoral Course Catalogue

Many students found the Doctoral Course Catalogue somewhat confusing at first glance. Some initially assumed that Agora itself offered PhD programs directly. Additionally, they noted that there is no information about the Unite! Doctoral School (UDS) available on the platform, making it difficult to understand its role and offerings.

Currently, the service caters to a very niche audience, meaning it does not fully address the broader needs of students interested in doctoral studies. However, students suggested that the service could provide greater value if it expanded beyond UDS courses to include insights, guidance, and useful information about PhD programs offered by all Unite! universities.

There was strong interest in PhD opportunities abroad, particularly in industrial PhD programs. Students saw potential for Agora to encourage them to consider pursuing a PhD at a university different from where they completed their master's degree, broadening their academic and research experiences.

5.3.4.1 Suggested Improvements

- **Enhance Access to PhD Information:** Include direct links to the PhD pages of each Unite! university to make it easier for students to explore doctoral opportunities. Provide clearer explanations of the Unite! Doctoral School (UDS) and its role.
- **Keep Students Informed:** Regularly post announcements about the opening of new PhD calls to keep students updated on application deadlines and opportunities.
- **Offer Practical Guidance:** Develop a “PhD Survival Guide”, outlining key steps, requirements, and tips for applying to PhD programs abroad. This could include insights into funding options, admission processes, and life as a PhD student.
- **Promote Industrial PhD Programs:** Students showed particular interest in industrial PhD opportunities abroad, emphasizing the need to better highlight the programs available within Unite! universities.

By implementing these improvements, the Doctoral Course Catalogue could become a more comprehensive and accessible resource, helping students navigate their doctoral journey with greater confidence and clarity.

5.3.5 Summary Feedback on Internship Opportunities

This service is of great interest to students, particularly for discovering internship opportunities abroad. Their feedback underscores its potential as a useful tool but also

highlights key areas for improvement, particularly in terms of visibility, usability, and content relevance. Ensuring that students remain engaged with the platform over time is crucial to maximizing its effectiveness

The students interviewed have not yet graduated, with some planning to complete their degrees by July. They recognized the tool as a valuable resource for securing job and internship opportunities. However, a common concern was that they might forget about it as they get closer to graduation, particularly if they do not receive regular reminders or updates. To maintain engagement, students suggested strategies to keep the service top-of-mind throughout their academic journey and transition into the job market.

5.3.5.2 Suggested Improvements

- **Enhanced Visibility of Updates:** Students suggested introducing a newsletter or mailing list to provide monthly updates and summaries of newly posted opportunities. While this feature already exists within the service, it is not sufficiently visible. A recommendation is to place it more prominently, such as at the top of the page under the title, with a clearer explanation of its purpose.
- **Expanded Job Listings:** Students expressed interest in seeing job opportunities offered by companies that collaborate directly with their universities. Strengthening partnerships with university-affiliated companies and expanding the job listings could make the service more attractive and useful beyond internship seekers.
- **Improved Interface and search functionality:** Students highlighted the need for a sorting function that allows opportunities to be organized by opening or closing dates. This feature would help users prioritize applications by focusing on the most recently posted opportunities or those with approaching deadlines, ensuring they don't miss key opportunities

6 Conclusions

The testing activities outlined in this deliverable are a crucial part of the development of the Agora of Acceleration Services. These activities are integrated throughout the key phases of the Design Thinking approach, providing continuous feedback and fostering an interactive, adaptive process rather than being a standalone stage. Specifically, testing is designed to validate the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) of the Agora and generate insights that will inform its scaling to the Value Solution (VS).

Our testing plan adopts a structured approach, dividing the process into three testing cycles: the first will involve individuals from aUPaEU's partner universities and additional universities from the Unite! Alliance and the EPiCUR Alliance to evaluate services and refine testing methods; the second will extend to new Alliances for which we are developing an Agora, to ensure the services' adaptability and scalability; and the third will re-engage previous users to validate improvements and gather fresh feedback, ensuring the services meet evolving needs across diverse Higher Education Institutions and Alliances.

Each cycle will involve interviews with co-creators, potential and current users, usability testing, focus groups, and surveys. This report outlines the timeline, main checkpoints to ensure alignment with other work packages, and the expected metrics for the number of sessions and participants.

Currently, we are in the first testing cycle, engaging participants from Unite! Universities. As we progress, the subsequent cycles will allow for further refinement of the MVS, incorporating feedback from a broader range of stakeholders. The integration of additional services and expansion of testing will provide valuable insights into how the platform can best support HEIs in their transformation processes.

Initial testing has yielded positive feedback regarding the perceived value of the first services tested, confirming they address user needs. Additionally, we have collected suggestions for improvements and identified potential barriers to adoption that can be addressed through further development and refinement of the services. However, to ensure the services meet the needs of a broader user base, expanding the user types in the short term is crucial.

In the final and future deliverable D6.3, we will report the results of the testing of the Agora, evaluate the feedback received, and assess the progress in the institutional transformation areas.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Interview guideline: Co-creators

Interview questions

1. Service Origin:

- How did the idea for this service first come about?
- Can you describe the initial problem or gap you aimed to address with this service?
- *Reinforcement question: What specific needs or pain points does this service address? How did you identify these needs in the first place?*
- *Reinforcement question: Verbally ask if they know of similar services, whether they have used them in the past, and then inquire about what this service offers compared to others*

.....

2. Target audience:

- Who is the primary target audience for this service?

.....

3. Adoption challenges:

- What challenges did you see as most relevant to its adoption?

.....

4. Current evaluation:

- Looking at the service in its current state, how would you evaluate it?
- Do you think it still meets the original problem or needs?

.....

5. Future Outlook:

- How do you envision the service evolving in the future?
- Do you see any opportunities for expansion or further improvements?

.....

8.2 Interview guideline: Potential users

Interview questions

1. Service Introduction:

- What are your initial thoughts on the services we just introduced?
 - What do you find particularly valuable about this service?
 - What about this service does not feel valuable?
 - *Reinforcement question: Verbally ask if they know of similar services, whether they have used them in the past, and then inquire about what this service offers compared to others*
-

2. Potential Impact:

- Do you think our proposed solution could help address your needs?
 - If yes, in what specific ways?
-

3. Adoption challenges:

- What challenges did you see as most relevant to its adoption?
-

4. Feedback and suggestions:

- Do you have any suggestions for improving the services? How could this service, or overall concept be improved?
 - Are there additional features or functionalities you would like to see?
 - What potential barriers to adoption do you foresee, and how might we address them?
-

5. Closing:

- How would you like to stay updated on the development of these services??
-

8.3 Interview guideline: Current users

Interview questions

1. Decision to use the service:

- What led you to choose this service?
 - Was there a specific problem or need that prompted you to start using it?
 - *Reinforcement question: Verbally ask if they know of similar services, whether they have used them in the past, and then inquire about what this service offers compared to others.*
-

2. User satisfaction:

- How has your experience with the service been so far?
 - Are you satisfied with its performance and the outcomes you have achieved?
-

3. Meeting needs

- Do you feel the service is effectively addressing your initial needs or expectations?
 - In what ways has it been most helpful?
-

4. Impact on your processes:

- How has using this service changed or impacted your workflows or processes?
 - Have you noticed any significant improvements or challenges as a result?
-

5. Areas for improvement:

- Are there any aspects of the service you believe could be improved?
 - What features or functionalities would you like to see added or enhanced?
-

8.4 Periodic Feedback and Improvement Report for Platform Services – Report #1

Periodic Feedback and Improvement Report for Platform Services

– Report #1

Work Package 6: Testing acceleration services and assessment of the user groups' progress in the institutional transformations

8.4.1 Catalogue of Research infrastructures

- Testing Target: co-creators and potential users.
- Role: support or management Research Infrastructures and Services

CATEGORY: USABILITY IMPROVEMENT			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	The research infrastructure profiles do not appear to be consistent. Specifically, infrastructures from certain universities are less detailed, which might lead users to believe that these infrastructures offer fewer services compared to others.	Standardize the format of infrastructure profiles, ensuring each profile contains detailed descriptions, high-quality photos, relevant keywords, and clear, direct links to the dedicated research infrastructure website. <i>This could be facilitated by assigning a contact person for each university to regularly update profiles and verify the accuracy of the information.</i>	
2	The " Filter by Keywords " section causes some confusion due to the way the individual keywords are written and their ordering.	Reorganize the keywords to ensure consistency, such as ordering them alphabetically and clarifying any ambiguous symbols or unexplained pinned keywords. Simplify the filter system to enhance usability, reducing unnecessary filters that clutter the page and compromise the user experience.	

	<p>Visually unclear design regarding optionable information in the Research Infrastructure Profile</p>	<p>Streamline the profile navigation by grouping essential information (e.g., "open to external users," "technical staff availability") in an easily accessible and logical order. Use visually clear design elements like checkboxes and avoid true/false statements to improve clarity and navigation efficiency.</p>	
	<p>The interviewees would like more information about the infrastructure to be displayed, not just as an indication that a research infrastructure exists for a specific field, but also practical details on how to access the infrastructure and the services and support it offers.</p>	<p>Add more information to the research infrastructure profiles, including details on remote access options (and what is meant by "remote access"), online booking capabilities (when applicable), the type of support provided by technical staff, their availability, and clear indications of the conditions for external users to access resources (such as whether training is required and the type of training needed).</p> <p>Visually integrate these related details into a coherent layout to enhance user experience and accessibility.</p>	
	<p>When users open the Catalogue of Research Infrastructure service page, they can see only three infrastructure profiles from the same university (without scrolling down). This may create confusion regarding the availability of resources and the diversity of universities involved.</p>	<p>Reduce the size of the filter sections to minimize their visual clutter. By doing this, more search results will be visible at once, improving the efficiency of the search process and enhancing the user experience.</p>	
	<p>At first glance, users may think that the link to the individual research infrastructure's website is unavailable or that the infrastructure doesn't have one. This is because the link is attached to the words "further information."</p>	<p>The link should be more prominent and clearly visible in the research infrastructure profile, ideally located at the top of the profile page.</p> <p>It should explicitly mention that it leads to the research infrastructure's website, rather than being labelled as "further information."</p>	
	<p>Some interviewees have mentioned that it would be visually appealing to have the</p>	<p>Add the logo of the university to which the research infrastructure belongs.</p>	

	logos of the universities connected to the research infrastructures.	<i>Suggestion: Include the logo in the research infrastructure profile next to "Home partner institution."</i>	
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CATEGORY: DESIRED ADDITIONAL FEATURE			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	It could be useful to have a search function to find research infrastructures with available technical staff to provide support for users.	Add a search filter for " technical staff available " and consider whether other characteristics by the infrastructure should also be included as filter options.	
2	<p>Target Audience Expansion: Currently, the service appears to cater primarily to researchers. To increase visibility among a wider range of stakeholders and establish new collaborations, it would be beneficial to use Agora as a platform to reach different audiences and promote the services offered by individual research infrastructures.</p> <p>If we want to open the laboratories to companies and increase visibility among a broader audience, some changes will be necessary.</p>	<p>Open the platform to companies and clearly specify which research infrastructures are available for business services.</p> <p>Suggestion: Add a dedicated section or filter that highlights research infrastructures available for business services. Make it clear which infrastructures are suitable for commercial use and provide a separate user journey for businesses to access relevant resources.</p>	
3	<p>Cost and Pricing Information:</p> <p>For research infrastructures, it would be beneficial to include pricing information for their services.</p> <p>However, this presents challenges, as pricing is often inconsistent across universities and research infrastructures.</p> <p><u>Challenge:</u> Establish a transparent pricing methodology adaptable to national and international needs.</p>	Consider adding pricing information for research infrastructures, while evaluating the feasibility of implementing it.	

8.4.2 Research and Innovation Proposals

- Testing Target: co-creators, members of the IRIS Network.

CATEGORY: USABILITY IMPROVEMENT			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	<p>Introduce clearer categorization between project proposals and other types of collaboration (e.g., joint papers or workshops).</p> <p>This would help research support offices focused specifically on project-related requests.</p>	<p>Introduce a clear categorization system that distinguishes project proposals from other collaboration types (e.g., joint papers, workshops). Use visual cues like icons or color-coding to make the categorization intuitive for users, ensuring that research support offices can easily filter project proposals.</p>	
2	<p>Currently, users are unable to sort proposals based on criteria like recency or upcoming deadlines, which can make it challenging to quickly find the most relevant opportunities.</p>	<p>Implement sorting functionality that allows users to view proposals by most recent or by upcoming deadlines. This will help users prioritize opportunities and stay on top of urgent proposals, improving the platform's usability.</p>	
	<p>Improve Visibility of Proposal Purpose:</p> <p>Currently, users must open each proposal to determine its purpose (e.g., research project, collaboration request, or paper co-authorship). A proposed solution is to add tags or labels beneath the proposal titles indicating the type of request, improving clarity at a glance.</p>	<p>Add tags or labels beneath proposal titles to clearly indicate the type of request (e.g., research project, collaboration request, paper co-authorship). This enhancement will allow users to quickly identify the nature of each proposal without needing to open it, improving overall user experience.</p>	

CATEGORY: DESIRED ADDITIONAL FEATURE			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	Request to develop a notification system for the IRIS network and, more broadly, for research support offices, to facilitate the dissemination of published proposals across additional channels. Once a collaboration request is posted, it needs to be disseminated through additional channels; otherwise, no one will see it. Each proposal should gain visibility through communication channels, which should partly be the role of the IRIS network. Typically, someone posts a request, and an email should be sent to the IRIS group mailing list, where proposals are shared. IRIS promotes partnership searches, but it would also be beneficial to send emails to university offices dealing with research or teaching, such as through the IRIS network or other networks.	Develop and implement a notification system that sends automatic email updates to the IRIS network mailing list and relevant research support offices whenever a new collaboration request is posted. Ensure the system also reaches other academic networks to increase visibility.	
2	Creation of a dedicated section for event organizers to easily locate relevant proposals. In past projects, workshops were often organized where researchers with shared interests were invited to collaborate on specific calls. This tool could serve as a matchmaking service, helping form initial groups who can connect during the event, exchange ideas, and develop potential proposals. Having a separate section for this purpose—rather than mixing it with other content—would make the process more effective and organized.	Create a dedicated “Event Organizers” section on the platform where proposals relevant to workshops and collaborative events can be easily accessed. This section should include filters or tags to match participants with shared interests and encourage connections during events, streamlining the proposal development process.	

8.4.3 Doctoral Course Catalogue

- Testing Target: Master’s degree students, currently in the final stage of their studies.

CATEGORY: USABILITY IMPROVEMENT			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	<p>Initial Impressions:</p> <p>The page was perceived as somewhat confusing. At first glance, students assumed that Agora offered PhD programs directly.</p>	<p>Revise the website's landing page to clearly explain the purpose of this service. Add a brief introductory section or banner explicitly stating that Agora facilitates access to opportunities but does not directly offer PhD programs.</p>	
2	<p>Lack of Information on the Unite! Doctoral School (UDS):</p> <p>Students noted that there is no information provided on the website about the UDS.</p>	<p>Add a dedicated section to the platform with detailed information about the Unite! Doctoral School, its objectives, benefits, and available programs, to address this knowledge gap.</p>	

CATEGORY: DESIRED ADDITIONAL FEATURE			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	<p>Students expressed interest in seeing job opportunities offered by companies that collaborate directly with their universities.</p>	<p>Discuss with universities about the possibility to integrate job postings from their partner companies into the platform. Possibility of creating a dedicated section or filter labelled “University Partner Opportunities” to make these listings easily accessible to students. Additionally, establish a process for regularly updating these listings in collaboration with university career services.</p>	
2	<p>Students expressed interest in exploring opportunities to pursue a PhD at a different university than the one where</p>	<p>Create a dedicated section with direct links to Unite! university pages that</p>	

	they are completing their degree. They believe that Agora could play a key role in helping them access PhD opportunities at Unite! Universities and provide support in the initial stages of their research journey.	detail PhD opportunities. Ensure these links are kept up to date.	
3	Students expressed interest in exploring opportunities to pursue a PhD at a different university than the one where they are completing their degree. They believe that Agora could play a key role in helping them access PhD opportunities at Unite! Universities and provide support in the initial stages of their research journey.	Implement a feature to announce and highlight new PhD call openings on the platform. This could be through a dedicated “News” section or pop-up notification.	
4	Students expressed interest in exploring opportunities to pursue a PhD at a different university than the one where they are completing their degree. They believe that Agora could play a key role in helping them access PhD opportunities at Unite! Universities and provide support in the initial stages of their research journey.	Develop and host a “PhD Survival Guide” as a downloadable resource or webpage, providing a step-by-step guide and tips for students pursuing PhDs abroad.	
5	Industrial PhDs: Students expressed particular interest in opportunities for industrial PhD programs abroad.	Collaborate with partner universities and industries to highlight these programs.	

8.4.4 Internship Opportunities

- Testing Target: master degree students, currently in the final stage of their studies.

CATEGORY: USABILITY IMPROVEMENT			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	Students suggested introducing a newsletter or mailing list to provide monthly updates and summaries of newly posted opportunities. While this feature already exists within the service, it is not sufficiently visible. A recommendation is to place it more prominently, such as at the top of the page under the title, with a clearer explanation of its purpose.	Increase the visibility of the existing newsletter or mailing list feature by repositioning it prominently at the top of the page, directly under the title. Include a concise and clear explanation of its purpose (e.g., "Sign up to receive monthly updates and summaries of newly posted opportunities") to ensure users understand its value and are encouraged to subscribe.	
2	Students highlighted the need for a sorting function that allows opportunities to be organized by opening or closing dates. This would enable users to prioritize viewing the most recently posted opportunities or those with upcoming application deadlines.	Implement a sorting function in the platform that allows users to organize opportunities based on opening and closing dates. Ensure that the feature enables users to prioritize viewing opportunities with the most recent posting dates or the closest upcoming application deadlines, improving usability and user experience.	

CATEGORY: DESIRED ADDITIONAL FEATURE			
N	Feedback Description	Actionable Insights	Approved or rejected?
1	Students expressed interest in seeing job opportunities offered by companies that collaborate directly with their universities.	Discuss with universities about the possibility to integrate job postings from their partner companies into the platform. Possibility of creating a dedicated section or filter labeled	

		<p>“University Partner Opportunities” to make these listings easily accessible to students. Additionally, establish a process for regularly updating these listings in collaboration with university career services.</p>	
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